

Guidelines for the application of integrated methodologies for the material, technical-constructive, chronological and functional documentation and description of human-environment contexts, historic buildings and multi-layered artefacts with a strong cultural value in their current state of conservation

Spoke 6 – History, Conservation and Restoration of Cultural Heritage

WP1: Anamnesi: Leader UNICT; Participants: UNICT, ICR, UNIMI, UNIBO, UNITO, UNISOB

Table of content

	PART I – Guidelines for the application of integrated methodologies	5
1.	Introduction	5
2.	Analysis and documentation of natural and human induced risk for CH	6
	2.1 Analysis of the types of risk, natural and anthropic, also in relation to the location (UniBO: Vandini)	6
	2.2 A post covid scenario (UniNA: Picone)	8
	2.3 A Special case: analysis of the seismic Risk (UniCT: Massimino)	8
	2.4. Suggestions for a protocol (UniCT: C. Nigrelli, C. Carocci)	10
3.	Analysis and documentation of multi-layered archaeological contexts/buildings and historic buildings	11
	3.1 Introduction (Militello)	11
	3.2 Taxonomy (UniCT: Laneri)	11
	3.3 Analysis of epigraphical sources (UniCT: Licandro)	13
	3.4 Analysis of topographical Context (UniCT: Malfitana)	14
	3.5 Analysis of the local context (UniCT: Gerogiannis/Puglisi)	15
	3.6 Methodology of documentation of excavation and stratigraphy (UniCT: Gerogiannis/Puglisi)	15
	3.7 Analysis and documentation of Historic buildings (UniSOB: Rossi)	17
4.	Analysis and documentation of artifacts	19

4.1 Methodology of analysis and documentation of artifacts from archaeological excavations (UniCT: Gerogiannis/Puglisi)	19
4.2 Methodology of analysis and documentation of Works of art (OPD: Gennaioli, Rossi)	19
4.3 Methodology of analysis and documentation of Bioarchaeological remains (UniBO: Belcastro)	20
4.4. Methodology of analysis and documentation of faunal remains (UniCT)	21
5. Analysis and documentation of material features and degradation morphology for restoration	25
5.1 Analysis and description of the monument/site (UniBO: Vandini)	25
5.2 Documentation and analysis of degradation morphologies affecting cultural heritage (UniBO: Vandini)	27
5.3 Stone (UniCT: Barone, Mazzoleni)	28
5.4 Mud bricks (UniCT: Laneri)	44
5.5 Metals (UniBO: Vandini)	44
5.6 Glass (UniBO: Vandini)	45
6. Proposal of Intervention, conservation and restoration	47
6.1 History and theory of conservative restoration (UniTO: Failla)	47
6.2 Restoration of works of art (OPD: Gennaioli, Rossi)	49
6.3 Conservation of wall painting in the Hypogaeal contexts (ICR: Sobrà, Capanna, Mezzadri, Valentini)	50
6.4 Preservation of contemporary public art in the open air (ICR)	52
6.5 Restoration of bioarchaeological remains (UniBO: Belcastro)	53

7. Design of a communication plan and a public engagement strategy for CH assets (1563)	55
Background	55
Guidelines on communication strategy for stakeholders and CH experts	56
Guidelines on communication strategy for general public	56
8. Sharing the data: digitisation and platforms (UniCT: Stanco)	58
PART II - A few case studies	61
1. The Pompei Project (UniNA)	61
2. The Baia Project (UniSOB)	64
3. The Royal Museums in Turin (UniTO)	66
4. Monuments and fountains in the city of Turin public space (1563)	67
5. Pompeii, the House of the Ancient Hunt (VII,4,47) (UniTO)	72

PART I – Guidelines for the application of integrated methodologies

1. Introduction (Malfitana/Militello)

The idea of Cultural Heritage conservation and restoration underlying the actions of Spoke 6 is characterized by the great attention it intends to pay towards the proposal of methodologies and techniques for documentation, analysis and interpretation based on the determination of shared standards and protocols, which translate into Guidelines capable of putting as a nationally recognized reference point.

This first deliverable represents a first step in this direction. It collects the expertise of the partners, each with his/her own focus, putting together their previous experience to create a methodological flow of steps with a proposed methodology. It includes analysis of risk, analysis of the historical and functional meaning of the artefact, analysis of its material features, analysis of current conditions and degradation, methodology of planning interventions and restorations, suggestions for a successful communication and digitization of the data, in order to improve the relation between CH and the public.

Obviously, what is here presented as a sequence can, in the field, correspond to actions carried on at the same time, nor it is always easy to distinguish from the documentation produced to better understand the historical significance of the monument and that produced to plan conservation or restoration.

This Guidelines have the aim, therefore, to create a theoretical model, which will, however be improved in the future following the results of the foreseen activities. They have not been conceived as a systematical approach to the topics of documentation, interventions, conservations, restorations and communication, which would be impossible in a 4 months period and perhaps also not useful, but as a series of suggestions organized in a theoretical sound sequence. As a consequence, some topics will not be found in all the sections (as the special case of the open air works of art, dealt with in section VI), and some aspects deserved a special attention as in the case of anthropological remains, dealt both in section III and in section VI, with a proposal for a digital restoration, or rock cut architecture.

The theoretical assumptions presented in these Guidelines have been the basis for the choice of the different case studies, which are presented in Section II.

The different case studies, proposed at the partnership level, will have the task of directing the research activities and evaluating the results achieved. For this reason, their selection, which was carried out right from the start of the study activities, was conducted in such a way as to guarantee, overall, a high representativeness of the chrono-typological, material-functional, technical-constructive and scale of contexts' investigation identified. In this last aspect, particular care was taken so that the case studies allowed to range from territorial contexts of great extension to the area of the single archaeological excavation, passing through intermediate steps consisting of extra-urban stratified landscapes, multi-layered urban contexts, sites and cultural areas in general and finally, single buildings and/or monuments.

2. Analysis and documentation of natural and human induced Risk for CH

2.1 Analysis of the types of risk, natural and anthropic, also in relation to the location (an urban monument has different risk factors from one placed outdoors in a remote site) M. Vandini)

Over the past four decades, the concept of risk related to cultural heritage has gradually changed. From the priority protection in the event of armed conflicts that emerged after World War II and the response plans to natural disasters – foundations that still hold true today – there has gradually been awareness of the need for a management approach and integrated assessments that thoroughly take into account the multiplicity of factors that define the concept of risk¹.

The conservation of cultural heritage, whether it be mobile or immovable, is actually threatened by hazards that have both natural and human origins. In addition to natural disasters like earthquakes, floods, whirlwinds, and tidal waves, the area is also at risk from human-caused hazards like the transportation of hazardous materials, the dumping of harmful substances, terrorism, armed conflict, and vandalism. The work of the Civil Protection Department of the Presidency of the Council of Ministers, a national organisation in charge of the prevention, monitoring, management, and reduction of risk factors brought on by catastrophic occurrences, has given Italian efforts to manage these risks its current form.

Today, each Italian municipality is required to adopt a distinct civil protection plan that outlines the hazards to which its residents are exposed as well as the mitigation and intervention measures that must be taken to safeguard them. The Municipal Civil Protection Plans list the Cultural Heritage as one of the elements of the territory that requires the most attention, but they do not provide specific operating procedures for protecting and safeguarding it during either the prevention phase or the intervention phase, restricting themselves to acting after the emergency has passed and primarily with the aim of returning the situation to how it was before the event.

The protection of cultural heritage in danger has been one of the primary lines of activity throughout the Horizon2020 initiative, and this focus is continuing in HorizonEurope². Also, organisations and associations like UNESCO, ICCROM, ICOMS, and ICOM that work on the prevention and mitigation of anthropogenic and natural risks harming cultural assets made a significant contribution with their suggestions and guidelines that were pushed internationally³. It should be noted that these recommendations are only a beginning point because, according to

¹ICOMOS 2019 "Future of Our Pasts: Engaging Cultural Heritage in Climate Action" (https://openarchive.icomos.org/id/eprint/2459/1/CCHWG_final_print.pdf); Vujicic-Lugassy, V and Frank, L. 2010 "Managing Disaster Risks for World Heritage" (<http://whc.unesco.org/en/managing-disaster-risks>).

² Some examples are the following: Interreg ProteCH2save – Risk assessment and sustainable Protection of Cultural Heritage in changing environment (<https://www.protecht2save-wgt.eu/>), Interreg STRENCH – STRENGTHening resilience of Cultural Heritage at risk in a changing environment through proactive transnational cooperation (<https://www.interreg-central.eu/Content.Node/STRENCH.html>), Horizon2020 HYPERION – – Development of a Decision Support System for Improved Resilience & Sustainable Reconstruction of historic areas to cope with Climate Change & Extreme Events based on Novel Sensors and Modelling Tools (<https://www.hyperion-project.eu/>) e Horizon 2020 SHELTER – Sustainable Historic Environments holistic reconstruction through Technological Enhancement and community based Resilience (<https://shelter-project.com/>).

³ ICOMOS 2019 "Future of Our Pasts: Engaging Cultural Heritage in Climate Action" (https://openarchive.icomos.org/id/eprint/2459/1/CCHWG_final_print.pdf); Vujicic-Lugassy, V and Frank, L. 2010 "Managing Disaster Risks for World Heritage" (<http://whc.unesco.org/en/managing-disaster-risks>); ICCROM 1998 "Risk Preparedness: a management manual for World Cultural Heritage" (https://www.iccrom.org/sites/default/files/ICCROM_17_RiskPreparedness_en.pdf).

the available information, the suggested action methods must be scaled down locally and tailored to the unique features of the region and its cultural heritage.

Last but not least, the necessity has emerged of moving away from a single-risk approach, in which the single cultural asset is "examined" in relation to a single impacting risk agent, to more realistic scenarios multi-risk, in which the multiplicity of potential risk factors that can affect the conservation of cultural heritage and which can occur either simultaneously or in a consequential chain is considered.

The examination of the different forms of risk can be broken down into the following steps in the following implementation phases of this line of the CHANGES project:

- Understanding the context: determining the risk agents affecting the selected case while taking into account the features of those territories and the types of cultural assets that are there (e.g. archaeological areas, monuments, historic buildings, churches, museums, etc.). The pre-existing documentation drafted by the relevant local bodies and entities (Municipality, Province, Region, Prefecture, Arpa, INGV, but also any pre-existing documentation held by the Superintendencies) will be gathered for each category of risk affecting the area. In order to develop models that may be superimposed on the current landscape, it will also be crucial to access historical archival evidence in order to understand the entity, scope in terms of determined repercussions, and periodicity of the catastrophic occurrences examined.
- Systematization of the documentation: the Cultural Heritage will be seen in relation to the urban/rural context in which it is located and its susceptibility to the risk factors impacting on it. To reach this goal, cultural assets will be appropriately georeferenced and superimposed on the thematic risk cartography relating to the territories of the selected case studies. By doing this, a database that can be explored and used will be created, enabling the evaluation and analysis of several risk variables at the same time.
- Analysis of susceptibility to risks and determination of action priorities: the ABC Method, which was developed by ICCROM and the CCI through the use of case studies carried out on a global scale and published in 2016⁴, will be used to enable an objective assessment of the susceptibility and subsequent vulnerability of assets to the identified risk factors. The ABC Method's use will first enable the definition of an overall picture of the risks that will have an impact, the identification of those that require urgent action, and the direction of operators, bodies, and local institutions in selecting the best responses to address those risks.
- Updating and monitoring: since risk management is a continual and cyclical activity, it will be important to periodically "repeat" the cycle to evaluate any potential changes. Changes in the environment in which the asset is situated, the appearance of new potential risk factors, or the accessibility of new information are a few examples of these. These can all help to improve (and modify) the outcomes of the preceding risk analysis and prioritising. Such a strategy will enable the implementation of the sustainability of the methodical risk management process, as well as supporting a more careful distribution of the available resources. Parallel to updating the risk management cycle, it will be possible to prevent the potential onset of degradation morphologies and/or alteration phenomena that could be indicators of an inadequate conservation environment for the asset by routinely monitoring the state of conservation of the monument, archaeological area, historic building, or collection with the aid of diagnostic investigation techniques.

⁴ ICCROM and CCI 2016 "The ABC Method: a risk management approach to the preservation of cultural heritage (https://www.iccrom.org/sites/default/files/2017-12/endangered-heritage_interactive.pdf).

2.2 A post covid scenario (Picone)

In the Italian post-Covid scenarios – in a situation of a progressive re-intensification of tourist flows and related overcrowding indices – it is necessary that research in the field of cultural heritage recalibrates its attention to the protection of the territory, increasing programmatic lines that aim to de-congest, de-localize, de-centralize, de-seasonalize and diversify. These require new approaches and new tools that converge in a procedural vision and in a culture of risk which, on the one hand, corresponds to the danger of the national territory and, on the other, to a vulnerability of cultural heritage, often aggravated by inadequate maintenance.

If until a few months ago the conditions of possible emergencies focused on the systematic violation of the *carrying capacity* of museums and archaeological areas and of the urban spaces themselves, subjected to an unsustainable "overtourism", today the new projects must focus on the themes of inclusive fruition, diversified and redistributed on times and destinations, as well as on renewed aspects of comfort and safety.

2.3 A Special case: analysis of the seismic Risk (Massimino)

The conservation of monuments and historic sites is one of the great challenges concerning the entire Italian territory. In addition to typical factors to deal with, such as cultural, technical, and economic aspects, mitigating the seismic risk of such historical-cultural heritage is a crucial aspect for most Italian cities, characterized by medium-high seismic hazards.

From this awareness arises the need to develop an **innovative methodology for assessing the seismic risk** and the **consequent protection of the historical-architectural heritage**. The impact of a strong earthquake on an urban community can be reduced with timely and well-planned actions. Assessing the seismic behavior of structures and the monuments inside them requires detailed knowledge of the **effects of the soil in seismic wave filtering (LSR: local site response)** and the **effects of the dynamic soil-structure interactions (DSSI)**. Accurately estimating the seismic input that impacts the structure is of fundamental importance to mitigate the seismic risk: it can change greatly from the bedrock to the foundation level. So, numerical analyses of LSR should be encouraged more and more. In addition, DSSI can lead to significant modifications of the free-field motion due to kinematic interaction. DSSI plays an even more decisive role when sliding and uplift occur at the soil-foundation interface. In many cases, the deformability of the soil influences the dynamic response of the structure, determining both an elongation of the fundamental period and an increase of the damping; consequently, the DSSI effects would be beneficial. Nevertheless, depending on the soil and seismic input properties, maximum spectral ordinates have often been recorded at high periods; in this case, the effects of the DSSI would be dangerously detrimental.

Preliminary analyses concerning DSSI are precious to estimate the seismic soil amplification or de-amplification and, consequently, to develop maps useful for the rational use of the territory and the seismic retrofitting of historical structures. In this case, effortless approaches can be used due to the significant number of structures to be examined. Accurate analyses regarding a single structure or a reduced number of structures next to each other can be performed by experimental models, simplified approaches, and advanced numerical modelling. **Fully coupled soil-structure analyses** should be performed to achieve an appropriate anti-seismic structural design.

Promoting **sustainable earthquake protection strategies is essential**, i.e., safety should be associated with sustainability. For a long time, the solutions for seismic risk mitigation have

required a lot of energy and produced large volumes of waste. Nowadays, eco-sustainability must be a fundamental requirement also in structure seismic retrofitting and restoration. It is essential to promote reliable, accessible, and sustainable earthquake protection strategies, furnishing innovative solutions for re-using end-of-life products, such as the new Geotechnical Seismic Isolation (GSI) materials.

The following procedure represents proper guidelines for an innovative assessment of the seismic risk and the conservation of the historical-architectural heritage.

1. Identification of different types of case studies (i.e., extended sites in urban and extra-urban areas and individual structures).

2. Collection of available data. A large-scale data collection will be conducted in the Catania area. The data collected will concern the soil profiles and the geotechnical characterizations of the involved lithotypes, thanks to previous in-situ and laboratory tests, and the main characteristics of the structures in the investigated areas. This information will be recorded on a Geographic Information System to create a Geodatabase.

3. Planning of new investigations. Other in situ and laboratory investigations will be conducted on the subsoil and the structures to improve the Geodatabase described in Step 1.

4. Definition of the input motions. The input motions at the bedrock will be selected using the Rexel 3.5 code (<http://www.reluis.it>), which allows us to search for suites of waveforms from the European Strong-motion Database, compatible with the reference spectrum in a defined range of periods according to the Italian seismic code (NTC, 2018). Synthetic accelerograms, according to the scenario earthquakes, will also be used.

5. Estimation of the Local Site Response (LSR) at the base of the historical structures

Site response analyses in free-field conditions will be carried out to evaluate the expected inputs at the historical structures' base level. The results obtained in this phase represent basic information and knowledge for planning interventions useful for retrofitting existing structures and designing new ones.

6. DSSI studies. Two approaches for studying the DSSI will be adopted: 1) preliminary studies at the urban level aimed at innovative seismic microzonation maps; 2) detailed studies concerning single case histories performed by numerical modelling and recording of microtremors.

1) The first approach will allow us to identify the critical situations for which more accurate, specific studies will be necessary. Based on the geotechnical characteristics of the soil, structure features and LSR, the spectral accelerations, considering both the fixed-base building configuration ($S_a(T_{\text{Fixed}})$) and the flexible-base configuration ($S_a(T_{\text{SSI}})$), will be evaluated.

2) For the historical structures characterized by $S_a(T_{\text{SSI}})/S_a(T_{\text{Fixed}}) > 1.15$ (possible DSSI detrimental effects), advanced 2D and 3D FEM numerical analyses of the fully-coupled soil-structure systems selected inside the investigated areas will be proposed and discussed.

Analysis of the risk. The LSR and DSSI analyses allow us to develop innovative seismic risk maps and a seismic risk data sheet per each historical structure. Thanks to this risk analysis, it will be possible to plan the necessary actions to protect the structures against the seismic risk: preventive conservation, seismic improvement and retrofitting, and recovery of deteriorated artefacts. All the results will be collected in the Geodatabase discussed in Step 1.

2.4 Suggestions for a protocol (UniCT: C. Nigrelli, C. Carocci)

Following previous assumptions, the following protocol of activities can be proposed:

- 1) Survey of the built cultural heritage and identification of natural and anthropic risks
 - a) investigation on the ICR-Carta del Rischio and highlighting of the gaps in terms of sites and areas at risk;
 - b) Identification, classification and geo-referencing of the archaeological areas and archaeological interest areas (both in extra-urban and urban contexts), of the historical centres and settlements.
 - c) Recognition of the documentation relative to natural and anthropic risks related to the sample area (PAI, seismic risk maps, microzonation studies, preliminary studies for the municipal urban instrumentation, anthropic risk maps, etc.).
 - d) Grouping of the surveyed assets according to the type of risks they are subject to and their relevance.
- 2) Selection of case studies according to the risks identified
- 3) Analysis, interpretation and definition of intervention criteria on the case studies identified
 - a) Historical and evolutionary analysis, on a documentary and bibliographical basis and by direct survey, of the artefacts and historical contexts examined;
 - b) Analysis (by means of direct survey and diagnostic investigations) of the current conditions of the assets examined, from a morphological, material and constructional point of view, and identification of present vulnerabilities.
 - c) Assessment of natural and anthropic risks (damage scenarios), also in relation to the type of case studies and their location in the territory or urban context;
 - d) Identification of risk mitigation criteria and strategies and planning of different types of conservation, restoration and valorisation interventions;
 - e) Extrapolation of procedures and models applicable to contexts similar to the study cases examined.

3. Analysis and documentation of historical and archaeological contexts

3.1 Introduction

In Italy, historical and archaeological contexts represent a large part of the material tangible CH. Theoretically, they belong to different categories of specialists, such as archaeologists and architects, but no strict separation can be made between the two. They share many of the methods of analysis and documentation (historical and archival sources, ways of survey and scanning) so that no deep divide can be traced between them. On the contrary, a continuum can be detected (think only of the Colosseum, or the Caracal Baths). The difference lays therefore not so much in the chronology of the building, but in its state of preservation and functionality. Both archaeological and monumental contexts can be long-lived and multilayered, but monumental buildings are still used by people and are planned to be used in the future. This implies the existence of a strong human pressure due to their current use (for exhibitions, offices, storerooms etc.) and the presence of different phases of use and reuse until the contemporaneity. Archaeological "monuments" are fragmentary, limited a few meters above the ground, only understandable as far as their plan is concerned but often of unknown use. Brought to light in recent years, they lost lively connection with the surrounding context. As fragmentary remains of a past living context they must be understood in order to create a new, even artificial, connection with the present.

In this Guidelines therefore the methodology for the documentation of archaeological contexts will be dealt in detail, spanning from the wider context (Topography, Local context) to the single monument or part of it. The same process can be applied to historic buildings which will be dealt on, however, only

3.2 Taxonomy (Laneri)

The following contextual typologies can be identified:

- 1) Subterrain archaeological/monumental sites within modern urban contexts (historic or prehistoric settlements).
- 2) Visible ancient architecture embedded within modern urban fabric (vernacular architecture, monumental architecture, funerary contexts, theaters, etc.).
- 3) Subterrain archaeological/monumental sites in non-urbanized contexts (historic or prehistoric settlements).
- 4) Visible ancient architecture in non-urbanized contexts (vernacular architecture, monumental architecture, funerary contexts, theaters, etc.).
- 5) Cave sites (i.e., prehistoric shelters, churches, nomadic sites).

For the architecture, it should be considered the following elements:

- 1) Stone architecture in urban fabric.
- 2) Brick architecture in urban fabric.
- 3) Wood architecture in urban fabric.
- 4) Mud architecture in urban fabric.
- 5) Stone architecture in non-urban fabric.
- 6) Brick architecture in non-urban fabric.
- 7) Wood architecture in non-urban fabric.
- 8) Mud architecture in non-urban fabric.

9) Wattle-and-daub architecture that can be raised or with only post-holes left on the ground (i.e., huts).

10) Above-ground stone caves (funerary and houses) without internal decoration

11) Above-ground stone caves (funerary and houses) with internal decoration (i.e., painted, incised or applied)

Regarding weathering, these are the agents that can definitely interfere with the site preservation:

- 1) Humidity caused by rain or vicinity to water sources or sewage.
- 2) Exposure to sun.
- 3) Air pollution.
- 4) Trash pollution.
- 5) Animal pollution.
- 6) Urbanization.
- 7) Seismic risks.
- 8) Fire.
- 9) Smoke.
- 10) Car traffic.
- 11) Climate change.

A further subdivision can be proposed following the position of the monument and its historical significance.

Urban monuments are those located within large cities, characterized by a heavy pressure due to overpopulation, traffic and pollution. Urban monuments can undergo two different situations, however. As part of an urban reality reachability can make their preservation easier, or, on the contrary, can make them more exposed to vandalism if located in urban degraded areas.

Extra-urban monuments, in rural contexts, are less exposed to degradation by pollution, but more exposed to natural risks and to abandonment. Their scattered location, moreover, creates what is called "minorCH" or "scattered CH" (patrimonio diffuso).

As far as the significance of archaeological monuments is concerned, a distinction must be made between those monuments which are widely recognized as "important", as, e.g., the UNESCO sites, and the majority of archaeological or architectonic monuments whose importance is less known.

From the point of view of procedure, the following steps must be followed for the reconstruction of the historical significance of an archaeological or monumental buildings

- 1) Research of historical/archival/epigraphic sources
- 2) Analysis of the topographical context
- 3) Analysis of the monument/Building.

For the archaeological areas, two further steps must be added

- 4) Analysis of the local context (for archaeological sites). As local context (as opposed to topographical context) we mean the wider area of excavations, including the single monument(s).
- 5) Excavation activity.

3.3 Analysis of epigraphical sources (Licandro)

Whereas the research on historical sources and archival documents is based upon well established protocols and a rich variety of documentation, so that the risk is more in the accessibility of these documents than in their availability, epigraphical sources deserve a special attention in these Guidelines.

In 1998, Silvio Panciera began his description of the “Epigraphy”, that should have constituted an entry for the Archaeological Encyclopaedia of the Institute of the Italian Encyclopaedia, writing: “L’Epigrafia è la disciplina che studia particolari testi detti epigrafi, o, meglio, è la disciplina che si avvale dei metodi che le sono propri per intendere a fondo non solo i testi delle epigrafi stesse, ma anche i monumenti od oggetti su cui sono scritte e, soprattutto, la società che ha prodotto le une e gli altri”⁵. Panciera introduced the idea of Epigraphy by including the epigraphic documents in their production backgrounds: urban complexes, public and private works, sanctuaries, and sepulchres in which the inscriptions were found, and above all social, political, economic, religious, legal, linguistics contexts of the societies that produced them.

Hence, Epigraphy is very useful for Scientific Research. According to a historiographical approach, it allows us to interpret the many forms of antiquity and to recreate the historical processes of a territory. In fact, an epigraphic document could be a very reliable witness, sometimes the only one in the absence of other sources; however, it is very useful if methodologically combined with the documentation of the manuscript, archaeological and numismatic tradition.

Today, the value of epigraphic documentation is further increased thanks to bibliographic repertoires and new specialized tools. These tools certainly include digital scientific editions, online databases, and many projects that encode material in the XML EpiDoc standard⁶. In fact, in the last twenty–five years, Epigraphy has reinvented itself and the studies about Ancient Greek and Roman world, through a wise digital approach. This essential meeting has given valuable results. The copious online editions of epigraphic *corpora*, that were prophetic in the recent two years, reveal a scientific precision inherited from traditional paper editions; but at the same time, they offer progressive tools that allow cross–research, publication of information in open data, interoperability between projects that involve different fields. The data obtained are entered into the scientific and virtual communities. Indeed, rigorous historical reconstructions are still conceivable only through the comparison between easily accessible and interoperable materials, sources, studies, information. Moreover, using this methodological strictness, the cultural heritage can be valorized in a territorial and historical dimension.

In this scenario, the condition of Italian Epigraphy is a complicated matter. A part of the very rich and varied epigraphic heritage is made up of known inscriptions, exhibited in museums halls or stacked in deposits. A part is currently lost and known only through publications (*corpora* as CIL, journals as NSA– *Notizie degli Scavi di Antichità*, but also works written by eighteenth– and nineteenth–century local authors and/or travelers). Furthermore, a part of the documents is unpublished and lies in the museums’ storage.

⁵ S. Panciera, *EPIGRAFIA: UNA VOCE SOPPRESSA*, in *Archeologia Classica* 50 (1998), p. 313.

⁶ “EpiDoc is an international, collaborative effort that provides guidelines and tools for encoding scholarly and educational editions of ancient documents. [...] EpiDoc specifies a subset of the Text Encoding initiative’s standard for the representation of texts in digital form using the Extensible Markup Language (XML) a technical standard promulgated by the World–Wide Web Consortium. It addresses not only the transcription and editorial preparation of the texts themselves, but also the history, materiality, and metadata of the objects on which the texts appear (see <https://epidoc.stoa.org/gl/latest/index.html>). Among the many projects see EAGLE, the *Electronic Archive of Greek and Latin Epigraphy*, today the *Europeana network of Ancient Greek and Latin Epigraphy* (see <https://www.eagle-network.eu/eagle-project/who-we-are/>).

Therefore, this nebulous condition represents a limit for the reconstruction of the history of the inscriptions, but also of the events that involved them. However, in recent years, considerable progress has been made, through excellent scientific editions of unpublished materials or updates of known ones, but also thanks to innovative projects. A good example is the I.Sicily project, supported by the University of Oxford and directed by Prof. J.R.W. Prag, in collaboration with various institutions, Sicilian museums and archaeological sites. I.Sicily – Building a digital corpus of Sicilian inscriptions aims to build and make available online the whole corpus of the inscriptions of ancient Sicily. A similar methodological approach concerned the EpiCUM (Epigraphs of Castello Ursino Museum) project, which represents the digital edition of the epigraphic collection of the Museo civico Castello Ursino based in Catania⁷.

3.4 Analysis of topographical context (Malfitana)

Among the objectives briefly mentioned above, an extremely important place is held, right from the start-up phases of research, by the definition of Guidelines for the documentation and the study of topographical context in which historical-archaeological evidence is inserted. If the conduct of a topographic survey requires a multidisciplinary approach that allows for a thorough analysis of landscape, interpreted as the result of the close relationship between nature and man, the definition of Guidelines involves the determination of the methodological-procedural and technical-construction aspects both for the collection and documentation phases, as well as for the analysis and sharing of results.

In order to properly circumscribe the scope of investigation, it should be remembered that in a topographical context coexist two types of data⁸: physical-environmental and anthropic-cultural. All the data contributing to the description of the natural environment characteristics refer to the first group, while those describing human actions in their “materic translation” and in their execution through the changes on the natural environment refer to the second group. Data that can be inferred not only from a context of the investigation direct analysis, but also from ancient and modern literary sources, inscriptions, toponymy, archival-documentary data and ethnographic sources⁹. The approach must be diachronic¹⁰, *i.e.* considering the contemporary landscape as the ultimate expression of the historical development of a territory and starting point for any investigation¹¹.

If the quality of achieved results with a topographic survey can be evaluated in terms of correspondence – compared to the aims and objectives of the research – to the draft knowledge base, outcome of the processes of documentation and collected data analysis, it is obvious how the latter two aspects, “documentation” and “analysis”, require a qualitatively adequate reference base for the representation of the expected knowledge.

In this first phase of work, particular attention was paid to the definition of the technical-realizative requirements of this reference base. Starting from the identified case studies (Santa Venera al Pozzo, Greek-Roman Theater of Catania, Roman Villa of Realmonte) we proceeded to:

- Collect and analyze all the available technical cartography (CTR, cadastral maps, geological, geomorphological, hydrographic, environmental, land use thematic maps...);

⁷ The digitization of the material was supervised by Professor J.R.W. Prag of Oxford University and by the CNR IStC of Catania through the agreement with Patto per Catania – Fondo per lo Sviluppo e la Coesione (FSC) 2014/2020.

⁸ CAMBI 2003, p. 16; FARINETTI 2012, p.10.

⁹ CAMBI 2003, pp.76–77.

¹⁰ FARINETTI 2012, p. 11.

¹¹ FARINETTI 2012, p. 10.

- Collect and contextualize all available archival material (scientific publications, popular publications, local studies, etc.), including historical cartography;
- Collect and analyze aerial and satellite photographs from different historical periods;

The analysis of these data will make it possible to arrive at a reliable evaluation of the available data quality level and their adequacy with the research objectives, constituting the premise for planning future actions, which must, first of all, ensure the production and digital restitution of an adequate reference base through instrumental survey campaigns and the integration of different methodologies (Laser scanner, DGPS, close range and drone photogrammetry).

Riferimenti bibliografici

CERAUDO-PICCARRETA 2003 = G. CERAUDO, F. PICCARRETA, *Fotografia aerea archeologica*, in *Lo sguardo di Icaro. Le collezioni dell'Aerofototeca Nazionale per la conoscenza del territorio*, M. GUAITOLI (a cura di), Roma 2003, pp. 67-88.

CAMBI 2003 = F. CAMBI, *Archeologia dei paesaggi antichi: fonti e diagnostica*, Roma 2003.

FARINETTI 2012 = E. FARINETTI, *I paesaggi in archeologia, analisi ed interpretazione*, Roma 2012.

3.5 Analysis of the local context

As extensively noted in the methodological bibliography[1], characterization of the context of discovery is essential to ensure protection and enable analysis of material evidence of historical or archaeological interest. It should be clarified that the evidence of interest can be either immobile (archaeological site, building, tomb, etc.) or mobile (e.g., concentration of fragments) in character.

The context of discovery can be defined by focusing on the following key aspects:

- 1) Spatial aspects: spatial location of the evidence through reference to geographical coordinates measured by GPS and through georeferenced aerial photos taken by drone. When the site cannot be reached by GPS (e.g., areas covered by buildings or trees), a relationship must be established with suitable tools between the area to be geolocated and the nearest GPS-detectable points.
- 2) Administrative aspects: identification of the legal status of the area (cadastral ownership, territorial jurisdiction, administrative and protection constraints)
- 3) Geographical aspects: geographical characterization of the area (urban, suburban or rural area; upland, hilly, coastal, marshy, wooded area; underwater area, etc.);
- 4) Environmental aspects: identification of the natural factors that have influenced the formation and transformation of the context of discovery (floods, earthquakes, erosion, etc.);
- 5) Cultural aspects: cultural factors that have influenced the formation and transformation of the context of discovery (agricultural work, construction of buildings and infrastructure, reuse, recycling, and spoliation);
- 6) Relevant aspects for planning fruition and enhancement activities: accessibility, involvement of local communities, social context of reference (metropolitan area, degraded suburban area, backward area, etc.).

3.6 Methodology of documentation of excavation and stratigraphy

Archaeological excavation is an investigation aimed at verifying a research hypothesis or an emergency investigation aimed at the recovery and protection of an archaeological context.

Three main phases can be distinguished in an archaeological excavation campaign: a **preliminary phase** concerning site preparation; an **intermediate phase** concerning excavation activities; and a **final phase** in which the excavation concludes.

1. Preliminary phase

The excavation area is to be selected on the basis of the following preliminary analyses:

- Congruence with the initial research hypothesis;
- Legal-administrative constraints should be checked (state-owned area, archaeological park, private property, etc.);
- Investigation of geo-environmental conditions (coring);
- The presence of archaeological evidence in the subsoil should be checked (geophysical surveys: geomagnetic and/or geoelectric);
- In the case of sites that have already been investigated, careful research should be done on the bibliography and archival sources documenting previous interventions.

The area selected for excavation must be geolocated.

Before excavation activities begin, the site should be organized. Safety procedures must be followed and strategies for disposal of the removed earth must be defined. It must be determined how to remove the soil (digger, hand tools) and how to analyze the earth (flotation, sieving, sampling).

2. Intermediate phase

Archaeological excavation must be a stratigraphic investigation because the individual layers correspond to cultural actions that are the focus of archaeology.

Stratigraphic excavation should proceed according to the following steps well known in the scientific bibliography (E.C. Harris, Principles of archaeological stratigraphy, London 1989; A. Carandini 2010, Storie della terra. Manuale di scavo archeologico, Torino 2010; P. Carafa, Storied ai contesti. Metodologia e procedure della ricerca archeologica, Milano 2021):

- Identification of layers that are referred to as US (stratigraphic unit) or USM (stratigraphic wall unit). Each US must have a progressive identification number
- Characterization of US based on color, composition and texture
- Analysis of stratigraphic relationships between US (what is above is more recent than what is below)
- Documentation of US and USM: compilation of US/USM form (description, stratigraphic relationships, interpretation; see annex), graphic documentation (plan, section, and elevations); photographic documentation: indication of US or USM name and location with respect to cardinal points
- Excavation of the US, starting with the most recent and continuing with the oldest
- Collection of artifacts, possible documentation of location of significant specimens (collapse, in situ object, etc.), and storage in appropriate containers according to US of origin
- During excavation operations, the matrix i.e., Harris diagram must be set up.

Through this, sequences of stratigraphic relationships are reconstructed and dated and all the documentation acquired is archived

3. Final phase

At this stage, excavation activities are concluded and the work site is closed:

- All graphic and photographic documentation must be completed
- It is necessary to define strategies for the restoration and enhancement of the discovered evidence

- In the case of non-completion of the excavation investigation, a decision must be made on how to preserve the investigated area pending the resumption of work (temporary backfill, temporary cover, etc.).

3.7 Analysis and documentation of Historic buildings (UniSOB: Rossi)

In the case of Historic buildings and multi-layered artifacts, the Proposed investigative reconstructions is as follows:

- documentary studies relating to the planimetric configuration of the spa area and its surroundings (historical cartography, iconography of the places, IGM 20th century plans) for the reconstruction of the original buildings and the architectural and urban configuration;
- study of urban stratifications for the fruition and enhancement of the site which, starting from the second half of the twentieth century, has undergone various and substantial transformations related to the building and infrastructure heritage (road network and construction of the Circumflegrea railway line) adjacent to the archaeological area and museum. Hypotheses of graphic reconstructions are expected for the urban transformations of the site and its surroundings involving various disciplinary sectors and aim at enhancing transversal scientific contributions. Therefore, the study and analysis of documentary sources, historical cartography, as well as the periegetic, iconographic, and literary sources, and contemporary architectural documents are essential.

The characterization will concern the architectural-archaeological, diagnostic, restorative, conservative and maintenance aspects; in this sense, the presence of expert professionals in: history of architecture (ICAR/18), biology (BIO/01), expert in archaeometry, professional restorers of works of art, professionals in construction techniques of materials (ICAR /19) and in systems for detecting the contemporary state (ICAR/17). Historical-documentary investigations are foreseen for the knowledge of the territory and, in particular for the aspects relating to the archaeological pre-existence connected to the existing architectural stratification.

Preliminary diagnostic investigations are planned for the characterization of the building through architectural survey and mapping of the present degradation with the verification of the state of conservation of the building through the detection of the state of the places with expert systems (HBIM).

A) Risk Analysis

It is an archaeological site, open to the public, susceptible to a risk factor of biological contamination due to the tourist flow. Furthermore, the marked urbanization of the surroundings of the archaeological and museum area, which took place starting from the modern age, and irreversibly (from a building point of view) in the second half of the twentieth century, determines a situation of urban stratification of rare environmental alteration.

B) Analysis And Description Of The Building For Restoration

Knowledge of the botanical heritage and of the scientific (BIO/01) and bibliographic findings relating to the historiographical literature of the dynamics of urban development and historical-architectural stratification (ICAR/18) of the Campi Flegrei area in the context of the Campania Region (ref. Digital ecosystem of the Campania Region:

<https://cultura.regione.campania.it/it/web/guest/home>). Analysis of ancient construction techniques (ICAR/19) of the environments selected for research is foreseen.

The different characterization of the artifacts, distinguished by clay, metal, stone and coloring

matter, could constitute a sampling of data useful for defining different aspects of the research.

Scientific investigations in order to evaluate the typology of the constituent materials (organic and inorganic) of the archaeological, architectural and artistic artifacts identified as an object of research. Analysis of the substrate with scanning electron microscopy (SEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray fluorescence (XRF), optical microscopy on stratigraphic glossy section (OM); molecular biology analysis in order to characterize all biological communities and place them in the environmental context, analysis of soluble salts and chemical investigations of organic and non-organic components through the use of instruments such as gas chromatography with mass (GC-MS) and Fourier transform spectroscopy (FT-IR) ¹.

Thermographic and colorimetric surveys in collaboration with the CNR-ISASI (Institute of Applied Sciences and Intelligent Systems "E. Caianiello") of Pozzuoli:

<https://www.cnr.it/it/istituto/O24/istituto-di-scienze-applicate-e-sistemi-intelligenti-eduardo-caianiello-isasi>, a multi-year collaboration already activated with the RESTAURO_UNISOB degree course: <https://www.unisob.na.it/ateneo/restauro/index.htm?vr=1>

C) Conservation And Restoration Intervention Planning

On the basis of the results obtained from the diagnostic investigations (referred to in letters C-D) the planning of a type of intervention (maintenance, conservation and/or restoration) will be evaluated also thanks to the planning of innovative protocols for the elimination of bio-encrustations through innovative and non-innovative methodologies invasive (use of UV-C and microwaves). These interventions will be conducted by expert figures of restorers and diagnosticians (BIO/01, L-ANT/10) with decennial experience in archaeometry.

4 Methodology of documentation of human artifacts

4.1 Methodology of analysis and documentation of artifacts from archaeological excavations (UniCT: Gerogiannis/Puglisi)

Every human artifact of archaeological provenance has documentary value for the historical reconstruction of the past and therefore must be named, cataloged, and preserved.

1) Denomination is done by progressive numbering from an archival sequence.

2) Cataloguing should use as standardized procedures as possible, preferably those defined for the Italian CH by the ICCD (*Istituto Centrale per il Catalogo e la Documentazione*)[2], according to the following steps:

- Identify the class to which the object belongs (pottery, lithic tools, bone or ivory artifacts, wooden artifacts, metal objects, numismatic artifacts, building materials, sculpture, inscriptions, small finds, etc.), preferably following the guidelines of the ICCD for the archaeological finds[3];
- Identify the sheet with the most appropriate format for each class, preferably following the format "Scheda RA (Reperto Archeologico)" of the ICCD[4];
- Proceed to compile the sheet;
- Supplement the sheet with graphic and photographic illustrations of the catalogued artifact;

The sheet should contain the following information:

- chronological indication of the time of writing the card;
- denomination of the artifact (identification number);
- chronological indication of the time of recovery;
- indication of the context of recovery;
- place of preservation;
- description of the artifact: state of preservation, dimensions, material and technical aspects, morphological aspects;
- graphic and photographic illustration of the artifact;
- dating;
- comparisons and bibliographical references;

The sheet should be placed within a digitized database, that should be structured according to the guidelines given below.

3) Preservation of artifacts must take place:

- according to standardized archival procedures, suitable to ensuring the findability of the artifacts under any circumstances and by anyone entitled to access them;
- in a place appropriate for preserving artifacts from any form of degradation related to natural agents (dry, ventilated, controlled humidity spaces, etc.) or human agents (alarmed or permanently guarded spaces), and suitable for allowing the fruition of the artifacts by scholars (storage facilities) and, if the case, by the public (temporary or permanent exhibitions, exhibition spaces within museums or archaeological parks).

4.2 Methodology of analysis and documentation of works of art (OPd: Gennaioli, Rossi)

A correct and exhaustive analysis and description of the artefact/monument/site is the result of the in-depth knowledge of its historical events and its present condition, which must include:

C1) In-depth archival-documentary studies and the availability of a reasoned and up-to-date bibliography on topics of particular interest in relation to the artefact/monument/site, for the purpose of a correct identification of its tangible and intangible values, a necessary prerequisite for any research activity;

C2) Analysis of the environmental, historical and anthropological context, including the different locations of the artefact, if movable, its possible presence in collections and exhibitions, the function and use of the artefact/monument/site and their possible change over time;

C3) Knowledge of the constitutive materials and executive/constructive technique, and evaluation, on this basis, of the influence of the action of time and mankind on the artefact/monument/site. In particular, the correlation between the natural ageing of the constitutive materials in relation to the environmental conditions (light, temperature, pollution), the anthropic factors and the executive/constructive technique must be investigated. For this purpose, the support of scientific research and new technologies, including experimental ones, is of fundamental importance, through the setting up of a diagnostic plan which, according to shared protocols, must proceed from non-invasive area investigations to non-invasive punctual investigations, in order to direct any further in-depth investigations by means of non-destructive micro-invasive techniques and, only at last, destructive micro-invasive ones;

C4) Knowledge of the conservation history of the artefact/monument/site, in order to reconstruct, in a diachronic vision, its life over time, as deriving from the results of the actions explained in the previous points and in order to direct any possible conservation measures, again with the support of in-depth archival-documentary, bibliographic and scientific-technological studies, also to characterise the type of deterioration and to identify its possible causes.

For a correct and standardised description of the different classes of artefacts, it will be necessary to refer to the regulations and terminological tools drawn up and made available by ICCD, i.e. definitions, vocabularies and thesauri, necessary for a common and shared language, both in the data acquisition phase and for their correct availability and accessibility.

4.3 Methodology of analysis and documentation of bioarchaeological remains (UniBO: Belcastro)

Within the frame of cultural heritage, a special and peculiar asset refers to the anthropological collections that have scientific, historical and social values. They refer to many types of collections, the most of them, assembled between 19th-20th c.: human skeletal collections coming from paleoanthropological, archaeological and museum contexts as well. The human remains represent a relevant biocultural archive to explore biologic and historic values of past and contemporary human populations. In detail, the human skeletons preserve and record the biological and cultural variability, providing insights about developmental, and biocultural and evolutionary processes, contributing to the reconstruction of the past and linking the past to modern populations. In the prehistory they are often the only source of documentation of past population, ecology and environment. They are also an essential source of information of the history of the anthropological and, more in general, the scientific disciplines between the 19th and 20th centuries, of the shift over time of the scientific paradigms and are largely utilized for the current studies of human variability and evolution. They encompass also social value allowing to build and cement a common collective memory and identity, no longer define in terms of place, social belonging, or cultural affiliation^[1].

In detail, we refer to different types of human collections, those coming from Italian archaeological sites and museum anthropological asset of the University of Bologna that counts

the documented human osteological collections (DHOC)^[2]. The DHOC is among the largest collection in Europe, including more than 1,000 skeletons from Italian individuals died between the late 19th and early 20th century. They are especially useful due to the opportunity to control biological parameters which are typically unknown in archaeological or forensic cases. The relevance of the value of these collections has been also recently recognized by the Ministry of Culture^[3]. In this frame their study, conservation, restoration and valorisation may preserve them from the risk of decay. Indeed, the retrieved of human remains in paleoanthropological and archaeological contexts encounter the necessity to take decisions on how preserve and conserve these peculiar materials. Further, the risk related to degradation of human remains is also present in museum environment hosting anthropological collections. Thus, their fate is threatened, also considering the ethical concerns that are becoming increasingly central in contemporary scientific debate as a result of new, emerging questions and the development of novel analytical methods. Thus, considering their sensitive nature, nowadays this peculiar asset poses new issues to find solutions to better balance scientific research, preservation needs, and ethical concerns. In this frame, to better manage these collections, pursue the value and strengthen the capability of this asset, for highlighting their scientific value and use, for offering a support for their preservation and protection and a mediation throughout innovative communication tools, in the attempt to overcome emerging ethical issues, new digital solutions have to be improved and utilized.

[1] Belcastro, M.G.; Manzi, G.; Moggi Cecchi, J. (Editors) (2022) *Quel che resta. Scheletri e altri resti umani come beni culturali*. Ed. Il Mulino, Bologna; Belcastro, M.G.; Mariotti, V. (2021) The place of human remains in the frame of cultural heritage: the restitution of medieval skeletons from a Jewish cemetery. *J. Cult. Herit.*, 49, 229–238. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2021.04.002>;

[2] Belcastro, M.G.; Pietrobelli, A.; Nicolosi, T., Milella, M., Mariotti, V. (2021) Scientific and ethical aspects of identified skeletal series: the case of the Documented Human Osteological Collections of the University of Bologna (Northern Italy). *Forensic. Sci.* 1, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/xxxxx>;
Belcastro, M.G.; Bonfiglioli, B.; Pedrosi, M.E.; Zuppello, M.; Tanganelli, V.; Mariotti, V. (2017) The history and composition of the identified human skeletal collection of the Certosa Cemetery (Bologna, Italy, 19 th –20 th century): The identified Certosa collection (Bologna). *Int. J. Osteoarchaeol.* 27(5), 912–925. <https://doi.org/10.1002/oa.2605>;

[3] MiC (2022). I resti scheletrici umani: dallo scavo, al laboratorio, al museo. Ministero della Cultura. http://www.ic_archeo.beniculturali.it/it/294/linee-guida-per-il-trattamento-dei-resti-umani

4.4 Methodology of analysis and documentation of faunal remains (UniCT)

Animal remains represent a valuable source of information for the study of the human–animal relationship over time. Animals formed an important part of people’s lives in the past and the bones from archaeological sites may provide information on not only diet but also on care, hygiene, climate, status, season of occupation, hunting methods, breeding, domestication and pastoralism, butchery methods, industries, trade, and even religion and funeral ritual.

Through the archaeozoological study of remain from archaeological excavations, it is possible to obtain two order of information: paleoecological, useful for reconstructing the animal populations that lived in a given area and their relationship to their environment (which animals lived in the

settlement; what environment they reflect; what changes are evident over time and what causes they are due to etc.); and paleoeconomic, focusing on the ways in which animal resources were exploited by humans (what animals were exploited; in what proportions, in what manner; what subsistence pattern was in use etc.) (Tagliacozzo 1993; De Grossi Mazzorin 2008).

Archaeozoological remains constitute a category of finds that differs in multiple aspects from other classes of materials (pottery, lithic, metals), primarily because of the raw material from which they are made. Bone tissue, teeth, shells, and in less frequent cases soft tissue, cartilaginous and epithelial remains, as well as the remains of mollusks, fish, insects, reptile and bird eggs, sponges, and corals, in light of the organic component are subject to different decomposition processes closely related to the conditions of the archaeological deposit and the taphonomical factors that are occurring before, during and after deposition, which consequently determines appropriate excavation, analysis and preservation strategies.

Unlike most human bones, which are often recovered from sites in an orderly and systematic manner, animal bones can be found in different contexts and areas of a site. The vast majority of animal remains recovered in archaeological excavations are probably disarticulated, meaning that the bones do not lie in situ in anatomical position to form a complete animal skeleton. This reflects the taphonomical processes that occurred, the activities and strategies of animal resource exploitation, and finally, in some cases, may reflect the function of the area in the site. Occasionally animals may be found partially or fully articulated, particularly in the case of human burials in a ritual context. It is therefore important to verify during excavation the lying conditions of animal remains and in the case of articulated remains to pay particular attention to documenting the lying conditions.

Excavation and recovery methods

Faunal remains provide a wide range of information about a site, but only if they are excavated properly. The most commonly used recovery method during excavation is "hand collecting," relying on the archaeologist's observational skills. The problem with this method is a visual distortion that leads to collecting only the largest bones. Animals are of all sizes, and this method would result in a bias toward the larger species. In addition, human error in this method results in different items being excavated differently depending on the person digging, the light conditions, and the tools used (O'Connor 2000).

The most effective method for recovering animal bones is usually a combination of manual collection and sieving. This involves collecting a number of soil samples from the excavation. For animal bones a small sieve size is often required in order to retrieve even the smaller bones as these may yield as much information as any large bone. Fish, small mammals, amphibians, reptiles and birds are often vastly under represented on archaeological sites as they are difficult to spot with the naked eye. The size of such bones requires a mesh size no larger than 1-2mm.

Preservation

Once the bones have been excavated, it is important to consider an appropriate method of preservation. Like most other artifacts, bones can be stored in plastic bags. The bags should not be sealed to prevent the bones from becoming extremely brittle with moisture. When bones are stored, it is helpful to have at least two labels in each bag. Once the bones have been washed and the samples sieved, they must dry. It is very important that they are not exposed to extreme heat. If they are dried outside, never leave them to dry in the sun. The bones will dry too quickly and become deformed. After cleaning, restoration of the bones may be necessary, which must be

effective and reversible, this is functional for a better analysis of the faunal assemblage and, above all, for its preservation.

Post-excavation analysis

Laboratory analysis begins with the determination of the anatomical element and the species which can be done using comparison collections and specific atlases (Schmid 1972; Barone 1976; Pales-Lambert 1971a, 1971b; France 2009; 2017).

The identification of age and sex, which is functional for the recognition of exploitation strategies, is an important step in archaeozoological analyses. Mammalian aging is carried out through the wear and eruption of teeth and the development and growth of bones (i.e., the stages of bone fusion) (Barone 1976, Grant, 1982, Payne 1973). Sex determination is performed through measurements or sexually dimorphic characteristics such as the canine teeth of pigs, and the presence of spur on the tarsus-metatarsus of birds.

Once the determination process is complete, the next step is the quantification of the remains to establish the economic importance of one species relative to others through, the Minimum Number of Individuals (MNI) (White 1953; Bökönyi 1970); (it consists of the smallest number needed to count all the skeletal elements of a given species); and the Number of identified Specimens (NISP).

Finally, the measurement of the remains, which is particularly important in the specific determination, distinction of sexes, and determination of waist size. are often carried out by most researchers by resorting to criteria that are as unambiguous as possible; the osteometric manual produced by von der Driesch (1976) is particularly useful in this regard.

The analysis of taphonomic traces involves macroscopic and low-magnification and microscopic observation at progressive magnifications.

The traces, distinguished on the basis of the agents responsible for their formation, are divided into two broad categories: traces of natural origin and traces of anthropogenic origin.

Traces of natural origin are due to: exposure to weathering/wheathering (Beheresmeyer 1978); root action and mineralogical composition of soil/carbonate composition/corrosion (Fernández-Jalvo-Andrews 2016); animal action due to chewing by carnivores/gnawing or outcome of digestive processes (Fernandez-Jalvo-Andrews 2016; to human or animal trampling/trampling (Andrews-Cook 1985; Beherensmeyer et al.1986).

Anthropogenic signs include: cut marks due to slaughter and consumption of the carcass; percussion holes generated during intentional fracturing of bones; and burn marks. (Binford 1981; Lyman 1987; Fernández-Jalvo and Andrews 2016; Shipman-Foster-Schoeninger 1984.

Conclusions

Faunal remains are an important part of any archaeological excavation. How they are collected determines the accuracy of the final result, and careful planning is essential to ensure at least one recovery of all the different species on the site. It may not seem important, but once the remains have been removed there is no turning back, and if they are not properly photographed and recorded the information may be lost forever.

Bibliography

Andrews, Cook 1985 = P. Andrews, J. Cook, Natural Modifications to Bones in a Temperate Setting, *Man*, 20(4), 1985, pp. 675-691.

Barone 1976 = R. Barone, *Anatomia comparata dei mammiferi domestici*, 1, Bologna, 1976.

- Behrensmeyer 1978 = A.K. Behrensmeyer, Taphonomic and ecological information from bone weathering, *Paleobiology* 4, 1978, pp.150-162.
- Behrensmeyer et al. 1986 = A. K. Behrensmeyer, K. D. Gordon, G.T. Yanagi, Trampling as a cause of bone surface damage and pseudo-cutmarks. *Nature* 319, 1986, pp. 768- 771.
- Binford 1981 = L. Binford, *Bones: ancient men and modern myths*, New York, 1981.
- Bökönyi 1970 = S. Bökönyi, A new method for the determination of the number of individuals in animal bone materials, *American Journal of Archaeology*, 1974, pp. 291-292.
- De Grossi-Mazzorin 2008= J. De Grossi Mazzorin, *Archeozoologia, lo studio dei resti animali in archeologia*, Roma-Bari 2008.
- Fernandez-Jalvo, Andrews 2016 = Y. Fernandez Jalvo, P. Andrews, *Atlas of Taphonomic Identifications: 1001+ Images of Fossil and Recent Mammal Bone Modification*, *Vertebrate Paleobiology and Paleoanthropology Series*, Berlin, 2016.
- France 2009 = D. France, *Human and Nonhuman Bone Identification: A Color Atlas*. CRC Press 2009.
- France 2016 = D. France, *Comparative Bone Identification: Human Subadult to Nonhuman* (1st ed.). CRC Press, 2016.
- Grant 1982 = A. Grant, The Use of Tooth Wear as a Guide to the Age of Domestic Ungulates. In: B. S. Wilson, S. Grigson, and S. Payne (eds), *Ageing and Sexing Animal Bones from Archaeological Sites*, BAR British Series 109, 1982, pp. 91-108.
- Lyman 1987 = R.L. Lyman, *Archaeofaunas and butchery studies: A taphonomic perspective*. In: M.B. Schiffer (ed), *Advances in Archaeological method and theory* 10, 1987, pp. 249-337.
- O'Connor 2003= T. 2003, O'Connor, *The Analysis of Urban Animal Bone Assemblages , A Handbook for Archaeologists. The Archaeology of York Principles and Methods*, 2003.
- Pales, Lambert 1971a = L. Pales, C. Lambert, *Atlas ostéologique: Mammiférés du Quaternaire. Les membres Herbivores*. Editions du Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, Paris, 1971.
- Pales, Lambert 1971b = L. Pales, C. Lambert *Atlas ostéologique: Mammiférés du Quaternaire. Les membres Carnivores*. Editions du Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, Paris, 1971.
- Payne 1973 = S. Payne, Kill-off patterns in sheep and goats: the mandibles from As yan Kale, *Anatolian Studies* 33, 1973, pp. 65-81.
- Schmid 1972 = E. Schmid, *Atlas of animal bones. For Prehistorians, Archaeologist and Quaternary Geologists*, Amsterdam-London-New York, 1972.
- Shipman, Foster, Schoeninger 1984 = P. Shipman, G. Foster, M. Schoeninger, Burnt bones and teeth: an experimental study of color, morphology, crystal structure and shrinkage. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 11, 1984, pp. 307.
- Tagliacozzo 1993a= A. Tagliacozzo, *L'archeozoologia: problemi e metodologie relativi all'interpretazione dei dati*, *Origini XVII*, Roma, 1993.
- White 1953 = T. E. White, A Method of Calculating the Dietary Percentage of Various Foods Animals Utilized By Aboriginal Peoples, *American Atiquity*, 18, 1953, pp. 396-398.

5. Analysis and documentation of material features and degradation morphology for restoration

Introduction (Militello)

Along with the historical reconstruction of phases and meanings of a building or of an archaeological structure, the study of the evidence includes also the analysis of its material(s). As far as archaeology is concerned, stone is the most widespread preserved element in Mediterranean countries, since perishable material (as textiles, wood, papyri, canvas etc.) can not survive acidity of the soil. Also Mediterranean architecture is based upon stone more than wood (as, on the contrary, Central European and northern architecture). Therefore a special attention is paid in this Guidelines, to the documentation of stone material. In a lesser way, however, bricks are present, especially in the Roman era, and mudbricks plays a special role due to exceptional cases of preservation as in Gela or Motya.

For artifacts, on the contrary, baked clay, metal, glass and precious stones are widely diffused.

5.1 Analysis and description of the monument/site (UniBO: Vandini)

Analysis and description of monuments and archaeological sites, before any conservation and restoration project, has been a traditional line of research for everyone involved in the conservation of cultural heritage since at least the second half of the last century. This has promoted the development of new methodologies as a result of the interaction between specialists in archaeology and restoration of ancient monuments. An acceleration has taken place in recent decades thanks to the innovations imposed by digital archaeology and in particular thanks to the application of innovative methodologies for the topographic survey of archaeological structures.

The hope that modern technologies could increase our capacity to preserve cultural heritage was already clearly expressed in The Venice Charter for the Conservation and Restoration of Monuments and Sites (1964), which states that the conservation and restoration of monuments must have recourse to all the sciences and techniques which can contribute to the study and safeguarding of the architectural heritage (Art. 2) and where traditional techniques prove inadequate, the consolidation of a monument can be achieved by the use of any modern technique for conservation and construction, the efficacy of which has been shown by scientific data and proved by experience (Art. 10)[1].

Archaeological monuments are often complex structures, composed of multi-layered buildings made of different materials that deteriorate in different ways. In some cases, such monuments can be topographically grouped into more or less extensive archaeological sites. The more complex and extensive such sites are, the more rigorous topographical approaches are required. Furthermore, structures preserved in the open air or in urban areas, under particular environmental conditions such as those just expressed (see above point B), expose archaeological monuments to degradation that must be continuously monitored, using documentation methods consistent with those used previously.

Over the last few years, renewed focus on the conservation of archeological heritage, in agreement with the Guidelines of the Superior Council of Landscape and Cultural Patrimony, has had its most important application in the Great Pompeii Project (funded by the European Union), through a *programmatic system of organization and carrying out of works for understanding and restoration*, organized into 6 plans (safety, works, understanding, capacity building, communication, use)[2].

In 2015, as an example, as part of the Great Pompeii Project, the Knowledge Plan for the Planned Conservation of Pompeii was realised. On this occasion, a new map of the ancient city and all its ancient and modern surfaces (streets, walls, floors, mosaics, roofs) was produced on a scale of 1:50. The topographical documentation was used by multidisciplinary teams of archaeologists, conservators, architects and engineers to map the degradation and state of preservation. All the data has been collected in a digital database on a Web-GIS basis, in which all the data relating to the monitoring and preservation of the site, as well as scientific and archival data, both from the past and the future, are brought together[3]. The experience gained in 2015 in a complex archaeological site like Pompeii made it possible to develop a workflow that can also be adapted to other sites. Some improvements have been made to the project, thanks to some Italian universities involved in the project, with applications of non-destructive diagnostic analysis (such as geophysics)[4] and with the inclusion not only of surfaces but also of the volumes that make up the buildings (Building Information Model)[5].

Topographical layout of the archaeological site. In order to document and analyse an archaeological site, it is necessary to start with a topographical survey. All subsequent work depends on this and therefore the highest accuracy must be employed starting with the DGPS positioning method. Subsequently, the detail and amount of information can be increased by drones with UAV photogrammetry. All information will be collected in a geographic database (Web GIS). In the field of Urban Archaeology the database can be enriched with historical maps and can become a real map of archaeological potential[6]. The documentation of the archaeology of an archaeological park or a living site is necessary in order to plan conservation and enhancement measures, in line with the provisions of the Malta Convention[7]. Furthermore, the database can be used to share some data on the web, increasing citizen participation and making them aware of the value of cultural heritage preservation[8], as stated in the Faro Convention[9].

Analysis and description of the monuments. The description and analysis of monuments is necessarily based on their accurate topographical documentation. This must be produced at various levels of accuracy and therefore different scales, taking into account the three-dimensional development of the structures. In fact, it is only by considering volumes that one can go beyond the mapping of superficial degradation and also analyse the static lesions crossing the surfaces. The consideration of volumes also allows the archaeological analysis of wall stratigraphies, according to the methods of the Archaeology of Architecture, to dialogue with the analysis of preservation risks. For this reason, the photogrammetric documentation of surfaces, which is possible with Terrestrial and Aerial Photogrammetry, must be flanked by Laser Scanner Survey with the greatest possible accuracy. The topographic instrumentation can be enriched with Physical-chemical Analyses of the building materials and with Georadar and Thermographic Cameras (with Infra Red radiation) that can provide further information on the degradation present beneath the surfaces.

The Digital Archive. As anticipated, all information will be collected in a web-sharable topographic database (Web Gis), which can be continuously updated.

[1] <https://www.charta-von-venedig.de/charta-internazionale-conservazione-restauro.html>

[2] M. Osanna, R. Picone (eds), *Restaurando Pompei, Note a margine del Grande Progetto*, Roma 2018.

[3] <http://www.iccd.beniculturali.it/it/progetti/4593/grande-progetto-pompei-il-piano-della-conoscenza-per-la-conservazione-programmata>

[4] G. Sassatelli, E. Giorgi (eds), *Pompei Intra-Extra. Archeologist from the University of Bologna at Pompeii*, Bologna 2017.

[5] <https://groma.unibo.it/issue-2019/toniolo-bergamini-silani-topographic-survey-walls-pompeii>

[6] <http://www.mappaproject.org/>

[7] <https://www.coe.int/it/web/conventions/full-list?module=treaty-detail&treaty-num=143>

[8] <https://www.arcadria.eu/carta-archeologica-ravenna/>

[9] <https://www.coe.int/it/web/venice/faro-convention>

5.2 Documentation and analysis of degradation morphologies affecting cultural heritage (chemico- physical methods) (Vandini)

Assessment of tailored "best practice" analytical protocols, adaptable to classes of materials. Understanding materials Cultural Heritage represents the first step to be taken in the development of suitable intervention strategies, functional to preserve this patrimony. A fruitful dialogue between technicians, scientists, scholars and other professionals involved in conservation and restoration activities stands, thus, as a fundamental starting point in planning interventions to be conducted in compliance with scientific criteria. The dialogue with professional figures and researchers working in complementary disciplines relevant to the study of cultural heritage, is, for us, of equal importance, in order to properly contextualise scientific data, exactly relate them to the artwork under study and, last but not least, make results able to respond, from time to time, to questions we have been asked.

The chemico – physical methodologies has the following wide-ranging aims:

- Characterization of materials, execution techniques and technologies for the production of cultural heritage objects and contexts
- Evaluation of the state of conservation and identification of degradation morphologies
- Technical-scientific consultancy to support conservation and restoration interventions

To this purposes, the plan of a diagnostic investigation should individuate the aims, the methods, the techniques and evaluate the cost/benefit ratio of the analyses.

The diagnostic protocol consists of a series of steps¹²:

- **Overall inspection of the "object" (non invasive)**
 - Visual observation and photographic documentation in the visible range
 - Multispectral imaging documentation
 - IR- VIS –UV imaging
 - Thermography
 - X or g Ray Radiography and Tomography – TC
 - NMR techniques

- **Spot non invasive diagnostic (mostly in situ)**
 - Optical Microscopy (either fixed or movable, like USB-OM);
 - Visible Reflectance Spectroscopy (VIS-RS)

¹² The list of methods can be further implemented in selected cases

- Fiber Optic Reflectance Spectroscopy (FORS)
- Portable elemental and molecular spectroscopic techniques
 - X-Ray Fluorescence (EDS – XRF)
 - Raman Spectroscopy
 - Fourier Transform IR spectroscopy
- Non invasive spectroscopic techniques¹³
 - Particle Induced X or g Emission (PIXE – PIGE)

- **Laboratory Analysis of the compositional features (elemental, molecular, mineralogical) and alteration products:**

- Scanning Electron Microscopy coupled with Energy Dispersion System (SEM-EDS) or Wavelength Dispersion System (SEM-WDS);
- X-Ray Fluorescence (WDS – XRF)
- Laser Ablation – Inductively Coupled Plasma – Mass Spectrometry (LA – ICP –MS)
- Molecular Spectroscopic techniques, possibly on a microscopic scale (FTIR and/or m-FTIR, Raman and/or m-Raman);
- Diffractometric techniques (XRPD or m-XRD)
- Thermal Analyses (DTA – TG and DSC)
- Isotope analyses, when provenancing of materials is needed (SIMS – TIMS)
-

- **Dating methods (short-list, as a function of the category of materials)**

- Radiocarbon dating ¹⁴C
- Thermo or Optically Stimulated Luminescence (TL, OSL) or Electron Spin Resonance (ESR)
- Dendrochronology
-

- **Preventive conservation protocols**

- Microclimate monitoring
- Environmental analyses (pollutants and bio)
- Scheduled monitoring of the conservation conditions (possibly by means of non invasive and in situ methods)

5.3 Stone (Barone, Mazzoleni)

In order to analyze stone materials, it is necessary to carry out survey and diagnostic campaign of the monumental building through three thematic data sheets based on:

- i) architectural features of the building and its state of preservation (Sheet A);
- ii) natural and/or artificial building stone (Sheet B);
- iii) forms of degradation associated with natural and/or artificial materials (Sheet C).

¹³ This techniques, being non invasive, have portable versions but they are mainly employed in labs

The survey and the diagnostic study which are aimed at providing information on the material supports can also be appropriately obtained through on-site analyses by means of portable non-destructive instrumentation.

The survey sheets are given below.

A) SITE SURVEY DATA SHEET

A₁ GENERAL SECTION	
Site Name	
Site Typology	
Year/period of construction	
Current Use	
A₂ LOCATION	
Country	Region
Province	Municipality
Address	Geographic coordinates
A₃ SITE TOPOGRAPHY	
A₄ URBAN AREA AND LOCATION (e.g., suburbs, urban center, industrial area)	
A₅ RISK (landslide, inundation, industries, etc.).	
A₆ MATERIALS SECTION	
Type of structure (masonry and coatings)	
Construction technique	
Dimensions (approximately)	
A₆ STATE OF CONSERVATION AND REPAIRS (visual observations)	
Degradation forms	
Damage level	

Restoration interventions	
Restoration techniques	

B₁ SEZIONE GENERALE	
Site	
Type of material (natural stone/artificial)	
Name of the material	
Location on the site	
Use	
B₂ SPECIFIC SECTION- NATURAL STONE	
Classification (UNI 8458-UNI 9724-1:1990)	
Color	

Stone Surface Finishes	
Petrographic classification	
Rock type	
Grain size	
Structure	
Fabric	
Visible minerals	
Fossils	
MACROSCOPIC DESCRIPTION (EN 12407: 2007) (es. stereo-microscope)	
MICROSCOPIC DESCRIPTION (EN 12407: 2007) (es. optical microscope)	
B₃ SPECIFIC SECTION - ARTIFICIAL STONE	
Material definition (NORMAL)	
Color	
Stone Surface Finishes	
Mineralogical and petrographical description	
Grain size	
Structure	
Fabric	
Visible minerals	
Macroscopic description	
Microscopic description	
B₄ STATE OF CONSERVATION	
Degradation forms	
Damage level	
Restoration interventions	

Restoration techniques	
B₅ ON SITE ANALYSES	
Optical microscopy	
Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR)	
Raman Spectroscopy	
Diffuse Reflectance Infrared Spectroscopy (DRIFT)	
Portable colorimetry	
Rebound Hammer test	
Thermographic analyses	
B₆ LABORATORY ANALYSES	
X-ray Diffraction (XRD)	
X-ray Fluorescence (XRF)	
Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM)	
Micro-Raman	
Mechanical/physical characterization (UNI EN)	

State of conservation

C) DEGRADATION FORMS SURVEY DATA SHEET

C₁ GENERAL SECTION (details in sheet A and B)	
Site	
Type of material (natural stone/artificial)	
Material Name	
Location	
Employment	

C₂ MACROSCOPIC IDENTIFICATION PHYSICAL DEGRADATION FORMS (Classification of deterioration phenomena of stone materials according to the standard UNI 11182:2006 and glossary ICOMOS-ISCs)				
ITALIAN NAME	DEFINITION UNI 11182:2006	DEFINITION ICOMOS: ISCS	PHOTOGRAPHIC DOCUMENTATION	PATTERN
Alveolizzazione	Formation of interconnected cavities (<i>alveoli</i>) with variable dimensions and irregular shape.	Alveolization: Formation, on the stone surface, of cavities (alveoles) which may be interconnected and may have variable shapes and sizes (generally centimetric, sometimes metric).		
Colatura	Series of vertical and parallel tracks, typically due to the percolation of			

	rainwater			
Colonizzazione biologica	General terms: infestations of mold, fungi, algae, lichens, bacteria colonies or higher vegetation.	Biological Colonization: colonization of the stone by plants and micro-organisms such as bacteria, cyanobacteria, algae, fungi and lichen (symbioses of the latter three). Biological colonization also includes influences by other organisms such as animals nesting on and in stone.		
Distacco	Loss of adhesion between a thin layer and its support: generally, affects plasters, surface pictorial films of tempera paintings, mosaics.	Detachment/Blistering: separated, air-filled, raised hemispherical elevations on the face of stone resulting from the detachment of an outer stone layer. This detachment is not related to the stone structure.		
Deformazione	Loss or change in the original shape of an element: a typical case involves ancient stone headstones	Deformation: Change in shape without losing integrity, leading to bending, buckling or twisting of a stone block.		

	fixed by iron grapples, which tend to warp.			
Deposito superficiale	Layer of foreign, incoherent material such as guano, dust, or dirt, almost always removable by simple mechanical cleaning.	Deposit/Soiling: Accumulation of exogenic material of variable thickness. Some examples of deposits: splashes of paint or mortar, sea salt aerosols, atmospheric particles such as soot or dust, remains of conservation materials such as cellulose poultices, blast materials etc...		
Disgregazione	Progressive disintegration of material resulting in the progressive fall of pulverulent material or minute flakes, especially typical of sandstone and bricks.	Disintegration Detachment of single grains or aggregates of grains. Fragmentation Complete or partial breaking up of a stone, into portions of variable dimensions that are irregular in form, thickness and volume.		
Degradazione differenziale	Loss of material from the surface showing the heterogeneity of its texture.			

<p>Erosione</p>	<p>Removal of material from the surface caused by footsteps or exposure to the weather and in particular to the mechanical action of wind and driving rain, freeze-thaw cycles, and salt spray.</p>	<p>Erosion Loss of original surface, leading to smoothed shapes.</p>		
<p>Esfoliazione</p>	<p>Formation of flakes, i.e., sub-parallel small lamellae that tend to rise from the surface of the material, gradually detaching.</p>	<p>Delamination Detachment process affecting laminated stones (most of sedimentary rocks, some metamorphic rocks...). It corresponds to a physical separation into one or several layers following the stone laminae. The thickness and the shape of the layers are variable. The layers may be oriented in any direction with regards to the stone surface.</p>		
<p>Fratturazione / fessurazione</p>	<p>Formation of definite separation pattern and distinct joints, with mutual rotation or</p>	<p>Crack: Individual fissure, clearly visible by the naked eye, resulting from separation of one part from another.</p>		

	shifting between parts.			
Fronte di risalita	Massima altezza raggiunta dall'umidità di risalita capillare all'interno delle murature, con formazione dei tipici danni come la formazione di efflorescenze e sub-efflorescenze saline, la disgregazione e polverizzazione e dei giunti di malta e l'esfoliazione dei mattoni o conci di pietra.			
Graffito vandalico	Undesirable application of colored paints on the surface.	Graffiti (vandalism) Engraving, scratching, cutting or application of paint, ink or similar matter on the stone surface.		
Incrostazione e concrezione	Deposito stratiforme compatto e generalmente aderente al substrato. Si definisce concrezione quando il deposito è	Encrustation Encrustation is preferred to crust when the accumulation clearly results from water infiltration followed by precipitation.		

	sviluppato preferenzialmente in una sola direzione non coincidente con la superficie lapidea e assume forma stalattitica o stalagmitica.			
Lacuna	Loss of continuity of surfaces (part of a plaster and painting, portion of impasto or ceramic coating, mosaic tiles, etc.).	Missing part Empty space, obviously located in the place of some formerly existing stone part. Protruding and particularly exposed parts of sculptures (nose, fingers...) are typical locations for material loss resulting in missing parts.		
Mancanza	Loss of three-dimensional elements (arm of a statue, loop of an amphora, piece of a relief decoration, etc.).	Missing part Empty space, obviously located in the place of some formerly existing stone part. Protruding and particularly exposed parts of sculptures (nose, fingers...) are typical locations for material loss resulting in missing parts.		

<p>Patina</p>	<p>Alteration consisting of the natural modification of the surface, not due to degradation and perceptible as a change in the original color of the material.</p>	<p>Patina Superficial modification of the material perceivable as a discoloration, in often having a favorable connotation.</p>		
<p>Pitting</p>		<p>Pitting Corresponds to the formation of point-like millimetric to sub millimetric pits, generally not connected, on a stone surface.</p>		
<p>Presenza di vegetazione</p>	<p>Presence of infesting plants, shrubs, bushes, or creepers, often located in the mortar joints of a masonry wall, in cavities or accumulations of wind-transported soil.</p>	<p>Plant Vegetal living being, having, when complete, root, stem, and leaves, though consisting sometimes only of a single leafy expansion (e.g. Tree, fern, herb).</p>		

Rigonfiament o	Localized uplift of a layer of plaster, mosaic, or coating caused by loss of adhesion with the substrate.	Blistering: separated, air-filled, raised hemispherical elevations on the face of stone resulting from the detachment of an outer stone layer. This detachment is not related to the stone structure.		
Scagliatura	Formation of flakes, i.e., sub-parallel small lamellae that tend to rise from the surface of the material, gradually detaching.	Bursting: local loss of the stone surface from internal pressure usually manifesting in the form of an irregularly sided crater.		
Abrasione		Abrasion Erosion due to wearing down or rubbing away by means of friction, or to the impact of particles.		
		Mechanical Damage Loss of stone material clearly due to a mechanical action.		
C₂ MACROSCOPIC IDENTIFICATION CHEMICAL DEGRADATION FORMS (Classification of deterioration phenomena of stone materials according to the standard UNI 1182:2006 and glossary ICOMOS-ISCS)				
ITALIAN NAME	DEFINITION UNI 1182:2006	DEFINITION ICOMOS: ISCS	PHOTOGR APHIC DOCUMENTA TION	PATTER N

<p>Alterazione cromatica</p>	<p>Natural color change affecting the entire material due to chemical, physical, biological, or anthropogenic causes.</p>	<p>Discoloration Change of the stone color in one to three of the color parameters: hue, value and chroma.</p>		
<p>Crosta</p>	<p>Change in the surface layer of stone of variable thickness, easily recognized by its very hard texture and dark color. It detaches spontaneously from the substrate, which is generally disaggregated and pulverulent.</p>	<p>Crust: Generally coherent accumulation of materials on the surface. A crust may include exogenic deposits in combination with materials derived from the stone. A crust is frequently dark colored (black crust) but light colors can also be found. Crusts may have an homogeneous thickness, and thus replicate the stone surface, or have irregular thickness and disturb the reading of the stone surface details.</p>		
<p>Efflorescenza</p>	<p>Accumuli di sali (nitrato di potassio o salnitro) che si formano rispettivamente sulla</p>	<p>Efflorescence Generally whitish, powdery or whisker-like crystals on the surface. Efflorescences are</p>		

	superficie di una muratura o al suo interno nelle soluzioni di continuità del materiale (fori, lesioni o porosità naturali).	generally poorly cohesive and commonly made of soluble salt crystals.		
Macchia	Localized color variation of the surface, related either to the presence of certain natural components of the material (pyrite concentration in marbles) or to the presence of foreign materials (water, oxidation products of metallic materials, organic substances, paints, microorganisms for example).	Staining kind of discoloration of limited extent and generally, of unattractive appearance.		
Pellicola	Transparent or semitransparent surface layer of substances coherent with each other and	Film Thin covering or coating layer generally of organic nature, generally homogeneous, follows the stone		

	extraneous to the stone material (protective film, film with aesthetic functions, oxalate film, etc.).	surface. A film may be opaque or translucent.		
--	--	---	--	--

5.4 Mudbricks (Laneri)

Since prehistoric times, mudbricks have been used as a basic material for ancient Mediterranean and Near Eastern architecture. They consist of sun-dried bricks made through mixing mud with a binding material (i.e., straw) that was then used to build walls that were covered with plasters. For archaeologists, the excavation and conservation of this type of architecture is a very complex task because it requires a skill in distinguishing the matrix of mud-brick walls from regular fillings and, due to their unstable conditions, they can crumble apart and the walls can easily collapse after they are excavated, because of their continuous exposure to weathering (sun, rain, wind) as well as air pollution. Thus, it will be very important to define a strategy for their excavation and, most of all, the preservation of the excavated architecture.

In order to do so, we propose to use preservation of mudbrick architecture exposed during the archaeological excavation through the use of innovative restoration techniques to be implemented throughout the PNRR program PE 5 Spoke 6. In particular, we are planning the following conservative strategies:

- *Diagnostics and analysis of the state of conservation of the mudbrick during the excavation:* a complete diagnostic study must precede the definition of the conservation project and will include the study of the mechanical and chemical-physical properties of the materials, knowledge of construction techniques, analysis of deterioration and instability, vulnerability assessment.
- *Conservation interventions on exposed mudbrick architecture:* the mudbrick architecture brought to light during the excavation must be subject to an urgent safety intervention; subsequent conservative interventions will have to contemplate the consolidation of the structures (with particular attention to the top and basement parts most subject to deterioration and washout), the restoration of the surfaces and the protection from degradation deriving from atmospheric agents and biological aggression; as well as, the protection of the wall crests, and the planning of an adequate water channeling.

5.5 Metals (UniBO: Vandini)

Outdoor Cultural Heritage (CH) is prone to degradation processes due to the interaction among physical, chemical and biological factors, especially in polluted environments. In particular, the worldwide decrease of SO₂ concentrations, the relative enrichment in NO_x, O₃ and PM and more generally, the local variations in terms of multi-pollutants combined with Climate Change effects, create aggressive scenarios affecting the mechanisms of decay of CH materials.

For metal artefacts, conservation strategies consist in a preliminary documentation of the material constituents and degradation morphologies, then in the set up of sustainable and efficient protection strategies towards these aggressive environmental scenarios. To this regard, in WP1, the contribution is oriented towards the development of guidelines for a shared analytical protocol dedicated to the study of degradation morphologies affecting archaeological and historic metal. The following analytical protocol is proposed for the documentation of morphologies of metal degradation (microstructural characterization, study of ancient metallurgical techniques, evaluation of the state of conservation and identification of corrosion and deterioration factors):

Inspection of the microstructure of metal and morphological features of the alteration products:

- Ø Visual observation and photographic documentation;

- Ø Optical Microscopy (either fixed or movable, like USB-OM);
- Ø Natural Colour System (NCS) documentation of colour (if applicable);
- Ø Visible Reflectance Spectroscopy (VIS-RS) measurement of the chromatic features (if applicable);
- Ø Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM and FEG-Field Emission Gun- coupled with Electron Back Scatter Diffraction probe, EBSD) for the investigation and documentation at high magnification and resolution of micro-textural and micro-morphological features.
- Ø Focused Ion Beam (FIB) milling for the realization of *in-situ* cross-sections (without conventional cold mounting in resin).
- **Analysis of the compositional features of the alteration products:**
 - Ø Scanning Electron Microscopy coupled with Energy Dispersion System (SEM-EDS) or Wavelength Dispersion System (SEM-WDS);
 - Ø Spectroscopic techniques (FTIR and/or m-FTIR, Raman and/or m-Raman);
 - Ø Diffractometric techniques (XRPD);
 - Ø Biological characterization of bacterial communities present in the alteration products, so involved in the bio-deterioration mechanisms.

5.6 Glass (UniBO: Vandini)

The emergence of degradation morphologies can negatively impact on archaeological and historical-artistic glass, affecting both its preservation and perception of the typological and morphological features of the objects. The compositional properties of the glass and the conservation environment are both intimately related to the commencement of one or more types of alterations, which are frequently consequential in terms of time.

Recent years have seen a focus on the necessity to develop approaches and support strategies for the conservation and restoration of glass, with specific attention devoted to the degradation of stained glass windows as a result of their direct exposure to atmospheric conditions¹⁴. On the other hand, the comprehensive study of the degradation morphologies impacting glass from archaeological excavations has received only sporadic attention. Ranging from pristine, where no degradation morphology is detectable, to so heavily degraded that most of the original material has transformed into corrosion products, glass finds from archaeological excavations can be unearthed in a variety of conditions. As a material, glass is highly susceptible to the action of water; therefore, when exposed to this agent, the occurrence of degradation phenomena can affect the conservation of glass-made archaeological items. For the same reason, glass objects found in dry soils are generally in better condition than those unearthed from moist soils. Given the presence of water as a necessary condition, the burial environment and the chemical composition of the glass are the two key variables impacting the occurrence and growth of degradation phenomena¹⁵.

The rate of deterioration of ancient glasses is influenced by compositional features as well. Glass of a soda-lime-silica composition is almost twice as stable as silica-potash-lime glass: the greater the percentage of alkali, the greater their potential to be extracted¹⁶. The difference in composition of glass is the reason for the difference in deterioration between relatively stable

¹⁴ Majérus, O., Lehuédé, P., Biron, I. et al. Glass alteration in atmospheric conditions: crossing perspectives from cultural heritage, glass industry, and nuclear waste management. *npj Mater Degrad* 4, 27 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41529-020-00130-9>

¹⁵ Fiorentino, S., Chinni, T., Galusková, D. et al. On the Surface and Beyond. Degradation Morphologies Affecting Plant Ash-Based Archaeological Glass from Kafir Kala (Samarkand, Uzbekistan). *Minerals* 11 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.3390/min11121364>

¹⁶ Davidson, S. *Conservation and Restoration of Glass*, 2nd ed., Butterworth-Heinemann: London, UK, 2003.

natron-based glass and less durable plant and wood ash-based ones. Medieval European glass made from plant and beechwood ash—and, thus, containing higher percentages of potash oxide and alkaline earth to ensure its stability—is highly susceptible to deterioration¹⁷. Soda-lime-silica glass made by using plant ashes as fluxing agents would seem to be placed in an intermediate position between the more stable, natron-based, and less stable, wood-ash-based ones.

Lack of a shared scientific terminology for the nomenclature of degradation morphologies is the fundamental gap in the literature on the topic. The currently available international glossaries¹⁸ provide, in fact, technical terms and the documenting of exclusively stone materials and historic buildings. Moreover, no systematic investigations have been conducted to explore the deterioration morphologies and associated corrosion mechanisms that influence ancient glass, resulting in the lack of a dedicated analytical protocol.

Therefore, the contribution of the CHANGES project is oriented in two directions: 1) the development of a methodological approach dedicated to the study of degradation morphologies affecting archaeological and historic glass; b) the set-up of a shared compendium, providing both a database of explanatory images of the different morphologies of degradation and a scientific lexicon allowing their description.

In order to characterise the morphologies of degradation and gather the documentation that will flow into the compendium, the following analytical protocol is proposed:

- **Inspection of the morphological features of the alteration products:**
 - Visual observation and photographic documentation;
 - Optical Microscopy (either fixed or movable, like USB-OM);
 - Natural Colour System (NCS) documentation of colour (if applicable);
 - Visible Reflectance Spectroscopy (VIS-RS) measurement of the chromatic features (if applicable);
 - Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM-SE and SEM-BSE) for the investigation and documentation at high magnification and resolution of micro-textural and micro-morphological features.

- **Analysis of the compositional features of the alteration products:**
 - Scanning Electron Microscopy coupled with Energy Dispersion System (SEM-EDS) or Wavelength Dispersion System (SEM-WDS);
 - Spectroscopic techniques (FTIR and/or m-FTIR, Raman and/or m-Raman);
 - Diffractometric techniques (XRPD).

Prior to studying the degradation products, the base glass' compositional characteristics will be studied using at least one compositional analysis.

The proposed analytical protocol can be viewed as a guideline and, as a result, it will be adjustable and implementable in the choice of the techniques. Furthermore, because it focuses on

¹⁷ Newton, R.G., Davidson, S. *Conservation of Glass*; Butterworths: London, UK, 1989; Lombardo, T., Gentaz, L., Verney-Carron, A. *et al.* Characterisation of complex alteration layers in medieval glasses. *Corros. Sci.* 72 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2013.02.004>

¹⁸ ICOMOS-ISCS: Illustrated glossary on stone deterioration patterns (https://openarchive.icomos.org/id/eprint/434/1/Monuments_and_Sites_15_ISCS_Glossary_Stone.pdf); EwaGlos – European Illustrated Glossary of Conservation Terms for Wall Paintings and Architectural Surfaces (<https://openarchive.icomos.org/id/eprint/1706/1/2015ewag.pdf>).

instruments that are available at laboratory structures that deal with diagnostics related to the study of cultural heritage, the approach selection is based on the sustainability criterion itself.

6. Proposal of Intervention, conservation and restoration

6.1 History and theory of conservative restoration (UniTO: Failla)

Based on the observation that museums and archaeological sites only rarely 'tell' the conservation history of the works they exhibit, a history that instead arouses the interest of the public and not only of specialists, the guidelines envisage the elaboration of research results not only, as a matter of course, in specialized publications and through traditional methods and media, but, above all, through innovative systems involving both museum-goers and web visitors, where such innovative systems will be tested.

The objective is to experiment with new forms of content dissemination based on historical and artistic specificity, examined in depth in all its diversity, in the belief that digital technology can be used as a means to obtain knowledge of the discipline and of cultural heritage.

The concept of "conservation history" has offered a fresh and innovative outlook to art historical research. It integrates the traditional and crucial attention to the genesis of the art work with the reconstruction and analysis of what happened to it after its completion, ie, the "artwork story."

Modification and restoration vicissitudes, collection and exhibition history, visual and literary fortune are reconstructed and analyzed comprehensively, as evidence of the "life" of artworks in relation to more general instances of change, including mentality, taste, culture, materials, meaning and ideology, social structure.

The historical culture of restoration, when viewed through the interweaving of the conservation history of the artworks and their exhibition, can offer a significant contribution to the art historical discipline, in the belief that the museum, the place where art history is defined by comparing and historicizing art works, and restoration, which is a critical act and a milestone for the vision and fruition of the work, are two fundamental aspects of the genesis and development of Art history.

In terms of communication, Italian museums in recent decades have had to deal with the gradual and widespread emergence of multimedia and digital culture. Today, many institutions are gearing up to seize opportunities to enhance the value of their collection and promote activities through forms of digital communication. The appearance of museums on the network, however, a part from a few exceptions, does not seem to be an informed move, the result of a well-structured reflection focusing on specific content and not just on the technological instrument. The proliferation of apps produced and supplied to museums by individuals with diverse skills indeed does not always correspond to a careful reflection on the content information to be shared.

In detecting how behind Italian museums are compared to the best practices of Anglo-Saxon and northern European museums, the preliminary surveys, which have already been carried out, have also shown, at both national and international level, an almost total lack of consideration regarding the conservation history of works.

The basic point is obvious but underestimated: the history of art works, their secular "life history" composed of interventions, restoration, moves, sales, exhibitions, interpretations, copies, etc., is not available in museums and archaeological sites, or is confined to minimum amount of information (the provenance or the restoration sponsor). Insufficient consideration given to the conservation and collection history of artworks is reflected in museum guides and even in catalogs, where such aspects are generally granted limited space. This obliteration of the historical dimension of the life of art works produces in the public two major misconceptions: that

their present condition is the same as when they were realized, and that the museum is their natural and original context, and not an artificial and transeunte location, itself the product of cultural, political and economic choices.

The guidelines therefore conceived and intended to develop an entirely new 'cultural chain', dedicated to the history of the conservation of works of art, collections and monuments, according to a five-stage process:

- 1) RESEARCH: examination of archival, documentary, literary, iconographic, photographic, diagnostic, oral sources etc. and reconstruction and analysis of the works' "conservation history";
- 2) DOCUMENTATION: processing of the sources to implement the existing data bases (ASRI) or those to be developed (SBN Minor material), and further study;
- 3) DESIGN: elaboration of content, criteria and characteristics to create a new integrated communication of the conservation history of the works, through print products (information handouts, panels, guides etc.), multimedia (video, etc.) and the web (QRcode, sites, app etc.); design of a digital application for a mobile device to manage, develop and use such products;
- 4) COMMUNICATION: Production of communication tools, including translations in Chinese and Indian, in consideration of tourism trends and of the need to achieve culture "mediation".
- 5) EXPERIMENTATION: activation of integrated communication systems in museums and on the web; ongoing and final evaluation of the system in its interaction with museum staff and visitors.

Projects wishing to work in this direction must therefore fill the existing gap by working on two fronts. On the one hand, recovering a fertile interest, in the field of art-historical studies, for the history of restoration, collection and museology, which have produced pivotal studies on individual events, museums and personalities, and a variety of research regarding diagnostics, techniques and materials in restoration; a highly specialized and fragmented scholarly production in terms of methodology, context, typology (historical essays, restoration reports, information cards for restoration exhibitions, various databases, multimedia products, etc). On the other hand, embracing the general interest, extended to the non-specialist public as well, in restoration and the 'collection journey' of works of art, by developing innovative ways of communicating content. The objective will be obtained through research on a wide variety of sources (archival, critical, iconographic, diagnostic, oral etc..), paying unprecedented attention to direct observations of art works on the part of restorers and diagnostic experts, in order to concretely verify the findings from the sources and build a new wealth of knowledge.

A great added value is also the relationship with scientific disciplines and in particular with diagnostics experts. In this sense, a path of reflection on the conservation history of the works can open a dialogue with scientists in order to direct investigations not only to monitor the current state of conservation of the works, but also to understand what the causes were, including previous restoration work.

Possible objectives:

- Comparing and monitoring international experiences of new forms of communication regarding historical, artistic and museum knowledge, through digital technology: investigate new and faster data connection, both in the preparation phase, during visits to museums and in the course of itineraries around the region (eg. the international Museums and the Web project,

interconnecting Big Data, collections and heritage), and develop forms of participatory communication and continuous interaction between museums, cultural institutions and visitors

- Develop content and multimedia products on the conservation history of artworks, structured on different levels of thematic analysis, with great attention to language and to verbal, textual and iconic elements, and to fruition and interaction methods;
- Design a digital platform with web and social applications, in the belief that new forms of technology can be used as vehicles of knowledge for cultural heritage;

- Engage visitors – more specifically, various types of visitors – in the process of learning about the existing and the potential museum, at its location or on the Web, not just by proposing content but by encouraging their comments, in order to develop an interaction leading to a deeper understanding of visitor requirements and wishes;

- Demonstrate the ability to achieve, even in the case of extremely specialized topics such as restoration and the history of collections, good quality divulgation, which by exploiting the potential of innovative communication is able to reach both different segments of the population of museums-goers and potential visitors of our artistic heritage;

- Development of the concept and practice of “mediation” in the history of artworks, which intends to move on from the simplest “communication” or “dissemination” (unidirectional transmission of historical-artistic information), to a more extensive and articulate “mediation” of contents with a view to educating people in cultural heritage and developing citizenship rights.

- Analysis, design and implementation of software platforms capable of Managing the storage of the digital contents (backend)

- Allowing museum operators and curators to create stories; aimed at describing the life of the artworks (content management). This platform will have to provide tools able to organize contents not only in a flexible way (given the multiplicity of possible contributions) but also in a simple way, in order to grant their use even to non-IT experts.

- Allowing museum visitors to access and navigate the stories related to the artworks (frontend).

To this end, the contents produced by the research into the “life of the works” are more extensive than the traditional reading of a work of art and open to a variety of approaches: indeed, they offer a multiplicity of connections between specific historical-artistic facts and the best-known historical phenomena, thereby enabling general knowledge to be reunited with the history of artworks. Following the guiding thread of the “life of the works”, the events narrated will be able to cover extensive diachronies and reach into the recent past, thereby stimulating knowledge and individual memories that the project recognizes and intends to exploit as essential elements of the socio-cultural history of the works, the territory, and people. By uncovering the life of the artworks, it will be possible to retrieve personal or collective memories of a specific context.

6.2 Restoration of works of art (OPD: Gennaioli, Rossi)

Closely related to the analysis and knowledge of the artefact, and therefore to the complex initial evaluation of the tangible and intangible values of the work of art through the set of knowledge provided by the actions indicated in points C1-C4, scientific and historical ones, is the elaboration of the restoration project.

It is worth emphasizing that it must be part of a contextual, dynamic and co-evolutionary vision, which has to include the before and after intervention status, starting from the monitoring and analysis of the environmental and anthropic risk factors to which the work of art is exposed in its

context, also in relation to its use, from the planning of its possible handling, packaging and transport to its relocation. This approach, based on a predictive and systemic perspective, guarantees greater sustainability of the cultural heritage conservation, for which administrative and financial continuity must be considered in relation to the subjects variously involved in this complex process.

The criteria for the adoption of restoration materials must be compatibility, efficacy and retractability: from this point of view, the use of traditional or innovative materials must be evaluated, based on the study of the materials' behaviour over time and the state of conservation of the work of art, respecting the DNSH principle, by using materials that guarantee the safety of operators and the respect of the environment. Examples include the use of essential oils for temporary consolidation, cleaning, biocidal and protective function, or the study of cleaning methodologies based on the use of natural gelled supports, with the intention of developing a low-impact system that reduces the need for sponge rinsing, and consequently the mechanical action on surfaces.

Closely connected to the guidelines of the restoration project is the development of a programme for mapping and organising all the documentation produced before, during and after the intervention, which also includes the technical specifications of the instruments used to collect data. Their archiving, especially in complex projects, has to take place in an easy-to-consult system/platform for content management and suitable for fruition at different sharing levels.

6.3 Conservation of wall Paintings in the Hypogeal Context (ICR: Giorgio Sobrà (contact point), Francesca Capanna, Paola Mezzadri, Francesca Valentini)

The subject of preserving wall paintings in hypogeal contexts, due to the exceptional microclimatic conditions, offers one of the most significant challenges with regards to the conservation of Cultural Heritage. ICR, through the restoration projects conducted over the past decades, has collected a wide range of case studies on this topic, including the paintings in the Domus Aurea, in the Etruscan tombs of Tarquinia and, more recently, those in the underground Roman Domus of Positano, in the Hypogeum of the Cristallini in Naples, in the rock churches of Matera and in the rock tombs of the Decapolis.

Mural paintings in hypogeal contexts have as their main element of complexity the fact that they are immersed in a microclimate marked by a very high and fairly constant relative humidity. While this must necessarily be maintained in order to avoid the rapid transmigration of soluble salts to the surface and their crystallisation, it also imposes greater caution in the choice of materials and techniques traditionally used for the restoration of mural paintings and decorated architectural surfaces.

This is particularly relevant with regard to two conservative treatments:

a. Consolidation of the support and of the paint film

The subject of materials and techniques suitable for the consolidation of wall paintings in hypogeal spaces is inextricably linked to the microclimatic specificities of such environments. The materials chosen for this type of intervention should meet three main requirements

- not to alter the permeability of the substrate;
- not to be bioreceptive, so as not to cause the triggering of any colonisation by biodeteriogens
- not be dispersed in organic solvents, both for health reasons (hypogea are poorly ventilated environments) and because some organic solvents, such as short-chain

alcohols, can themselves be activators of the germination of spores of certain biodeteriogens.

Most of the materials usually used in consolidation, for example, consist of organic resins or alcohol suspensions of nanoparticles; their use in hypogeal spaces can therefore lead to a significant contribution of nutrients, useful for the development of biodeteriogens and their diffusion on painted surfaces.

For this reason, the most recent experiments in this field are focusing on the use of inorganic and, where nanometric, non-alcohol-suspended materials.

One of the most promising experiments is undoubtedly that of the application, as a consolidating agent, of latest-generation nanocalcium materials that, compared to other nanometric materials, have the considerable advantage of being suspended in water. The nature of this material also allows a step forward in the search for ever greater compatibility and environmental sustainability of restoration products.

Nanocalcium materials were recently applied, for example, in the consolidation of the wall paintings of the so-called "Crypt of Saints Peter and Paul", located in the undergrounds of the Church of San Francesco d'Assisi in Matera, as part of a degree thesis of the ICR School of Higher Education and Study, with promising results.

With regard to the subject of consolidation in underground contexts, it is therefore believed necessary to carry out a preliminary extensive investigation of the state-of-the-art, and then to define specific application cases on which to conduct experiments.

As a result of this, it will be possible to draw clear indications about the pros and cons of the use of certain consolidating materials in hypogeum and to define useful guidelines to orientate future interventions in the national and international context.

b. Integration and Aesthetic Presentation

The second issue worthy of consideration is the choice of materials and techniques used for the reintegration and aesthetic presentation of the wall paintings in the underground environment: here too, the issue of high relative humidity constitutes the main stumbling block to the use of the usual methods of intervention.

The materials traditionally used for the reintegration of wall paintings, based on gum arabic, do not seem to be suitable for this particular conservation context, despite their proven compatibility and reversibility.

The presence of an organic binder, albeit in modest quantities, can lead to all the negative consequences previously illustrated on the development of biodeteriogens in the underground environment.

In the case of watercolour, moreover, its pronounced solubility in water, poorly matches the high level of relative humidity present in hypogeal contexts, where surface condensation phenomena are very frequent, resulting in reduced durability.

Equally problematic is the choice of the most suitable mortars for grouting the lacunae, which should meet different requirements:

- a mechanical resistance that is not too high, calibrated to that of the original plaster, which is very often highly degraded and not very resistant due to its high water content;
- a sufficiently high porosity, comparable to or higher than that of the original plaster, to ensure the preferential escape and crystallisation of salts on the restoration plasterwork rather than on the surrounding original surface.

Studies in this field are therefore oriented towards the exploration of materials for paint reintegration that are not industrially formulated, but are self-produced, to ensure knowledge and

control of the substances present in the formulation. This will also make it possible to test out possible additives that can slow down or prevent the deterioration of the formulations themselves by biodeteriogens.

With regard to the subject of reintegration and aesthetic presentation in hypogeal contexts, it is therefore envisaged to proceed with a preliminary broad verification of the state of knowledge, in order to identify the experiments to be conducted on specific case studies.

Once this phase has been completed, it will be possible to define clear indications regarding the positive and negative aspects of the use of specific materials for reintegration in hypogeum, and to propose guidelines that can become a solid national and international reference for future interventions.

6.4 The preservation of contemporary public art in the open air (ICR)

Another topic that will be addressed is that of the conservation of contemporary art in the open air, a well-established field of study that is part of a broader field, that of the conservation of public art: a crossroads between the protection of material, aesthetic and social values.

Public art, in all its forms, is exposed to environmental and anthropic risk factors in its space, factors also linked to the social recognition of the work of art, before the normative one, which make it both fragile and open to interaction and contamination. In the case of contemporary art, at times linked to artistic messages that are not easily interpreted by everyone, the relationship of the work with the community becomes fundamental for the triggering of that social recognition that subsequently determines one of its most important mechanisms, i.e. the first moment linked to preventive conservation: that of common "care". The mechanisms and instruments of direct and indirect protection and safeguarding, both at a social and regulatory level, of these artefacts exhibited outdoors will therefore be investigated, also assessing the "limits" within which contemporary art in Italy is protected, that is, those established by the Code of Cultural Heritage, which largely excludes it from protection itself but, at the same time, in its form as public contemporary art in the open, it imposes itself on general enjoyment, becoming a generator of collective sense, a measure of the democracy of places. The systematisation of this information will be related to PACTA, "Protocols for the Authenticity, Care and Protection of Contemporary Art" and Guidelines for its Use.

Public art also plays a role as a social actor in urban redevelopment, especially in the architectural dimension of walls and its decorations, and, especially if it carries complex languages such as those of contemporary art, it can activate processes of conservation and destruction, rejection and adoption, acting as a testimony of civilisation, of a community, in the sense developed from the Franceschini Commission in 1964–1967 to the Faro Convention.

Increasing social awareness about the value of public open-air contemporary art heritage, as a factor of indirect conservation of the heritage, is one of the objectives this knowledge, experimentation and dissemination project.

Starting from the ICR's previous experiences in the field of contemporary public art, among all the particularly significant one conducted in recent years on the works of the "Piscina Arte Aperta" diffuse museum of contemporary art in the province of Turin, one of the objectives will be to systematise the main and different categories and classes of artefacts present on the national territory where the conservation of different constituent materials in the outdoor environment is determined by the type of material itself, by factors of social interaction, climate, atmospheric pollution, artistic production and creation processes, flaws inherent to the constituent material,

and human actions, which accelerate degradation processes (reference to the ICR Risk Map, with the addition of the so-called "social risk").

In particular, the materials of contemporary art, which are non-traditional and often industrially produced, not tested for outdoor use, and applied on natural and artificial stone supports and on the surfaces that decorate architecture, tend to increase the potential risk of degradation of these works, which are among the most important and representative of public art. Therefore, 'structured plans and guidelines dedicated to preventive conservation and planned maintenance' will be drawn up, with particular reference to these types of works that are more complex and subject to degradation, through direct and indirect actions on artistic artefacts that also include social interventions linked to so-called 'participatory conservation', 'citizen science' projects and policies for including the community in decision-making processes concerning conservation. Through these plans, it is hoped to develop the foundations for legislation on preventive conservation and planned maintenance even independently of the activation of an actual restoration project.

A further objective will be the study and application of innovative and eco-friendly methodologies for the sustainable restoration and protection of works of contemporary art in the outdoor environment, with a special focus on complex natural and artificial stone constituent materials, urban murals and street art, in the context of which a PhD scholarship will also be awarded to increase and acquire the results obtained within a broader research framework, developing solutions and procedures that also evaluate a possible role in the reduction of air pollution in the local area.

6.5 Restoration of bioarchaeological remains (UniBO: Belcastro)

b) Documentation, restoration, and conservation of museum anthropological collections and human remains through digital tools

Since the scientific, educational, and historical relevance of the human remains, it is necessary to affine protocols that can allow a best choice for their documentation, restoration, conservation and exhibition. Digital tools have offered new perspectives to address these aims and are becoming largely used in the last decades. The field of Virtual Anthropology exploits digital technologies from different domains such as medicine, palaeontology, mathematics, statistics, and engineering. This approach gives the possibility to create virtual copies of specimens, large dataset that will be permanently available, the reconstruction/restoration of specimens based on mathematical and geometrical approaches, as well as data conservation, exposing and sharing for research and educational goals[1].

Documentation: Beside the undouble value of traditional methods for documenting human remains, digital methods allowed several advantages for this specific purpose. Firstly, the virtual acquisition of bones allows to have an exact copy of the element that do not encounter the risk to be degraded by the action of the time, environmental agents, and human interventions. There are several protocols that are used to virtually acquire human skeletal remains, such as the photogrammetry, computed tomography (CT) or micro- computed tomography (micro-CT), and surface laser scanning. All of them have advantageous and disadvantageous aspects to take in consideration: for instance, laser scanner and photogrammetry allows to acquire only the external surface of the bone, and in comparison, the photogrammetry has lower-cost then the laser scanner. Also, CT and micro-CT use may require high costs and time-consuming for data processing, but they allow observing internal structures of the bone. Secondly, the use of digital models for anthropological research has the advantage of the portability. Researchers have the

possibility of analysing bones on their computer and to do not be physically present in the place in which the materials are stored. This could be considered a weak advantageous aspect of the digital acquisition of those remains, but instead it could be very important for easily sharing digital models with other Research Institutes spanned in the word and other researchers of the PNRR network, or to continue to work while in extreme situations such as the lock-down we experimented during the Covid-pandemic period. Lasty, the virtual acquisition of bones may promote the “open osteology” by creating open-source dataset of virtual skeletal collections from museums or archaeological context, facilitating educational and research activities[2].

Restoration: Human skeletal remains from paleoanthropological and archaeological contexts are often in poor skeletal preservation, incomplete and in fragmentary condition. Fragmented bones with cracks and/or gaps are usually discarded from traditional analysis because they cannot provide the required information. However, new approaches have been developed to virtual reconstruct incomplete specimens. Particularly, geometric morphometrics offer the possibility to virtually reconstruct missing data from partially damaged specimens[3]. Geometric morphometrics allows to capture the full geometry of an object or a bone using landmark and semilandmark data. Landmarks are anatomical homologous points that correspond in all specimens of a data set. Sets of landmarks can be recorded in 2 (x- and y coordinates) or 3 dimensions (x-, y, z-coordinates). Semilandmarks are not anatomical landmarks but when a thin-plate spline interpolation function is applied they became geometrically homologous between individuals, thus allowing for analysis in conjunction with traditional landmarks[4]. The use of semilandmarks allow estimates of missing data from the information that is present using the thin-plate spline interpolation[5], ultimately allowing the use of virtually reconstructed specimens for anthropological analysis or for exhibition.

Conservation: Building virtual collections can provide the possibility to permanently store this cultural heritage, to investigate biology and cultural aspects of past and modern human populations. The conservation of virtual skeletal collections may guarantee to use them in the future for research analysis involving new technologies, and for computing new techniques, offering permanent resources to ensure further and wider fruition. Further, in the case in which invasive analysis are requested on the original specimen (e.g., DNA analysis), the virtual models can be secured for other investigations or can be 3D printed for exposition in museum or educational activities. Since the scientific relevance of human osteological collections, Virtual Conservation would maximize the potentialities of the anthropological research aiming to explore and quantify human variability in contemporary and past populations, while also valorising, safeguarding and preventing the human osteological collections from improper uses and decay for present and future generations of scholars and citizens[6]. In addition, the virtual copies and visualization of original specimens may also allow for providing an alternative solution in the educational museum activities and exhibition, in the attempt to overcome the current and rampant issues related to the management of the anthropological collections, especially the human remains.

Objectives

Within the CHANGES project, a protocol for protection, conservation and accessibility for scientific and museum purposes of human skeletal remains, as well as other kind of asset, is proposed. The proposed protocol takes advantages from innovative virtual reconstructions and digital resources, and consists of the following objectives:

- A) Developing a methodological approach for assessing the state of preservation of human skeletal remains from archaeological and museum contexts, while assessing their risk of degradation.
- B) Documenting selected materials with the support of virtual technologies (surface scanning, photogrammetry, CT).
- C) Creating three models and CT volume visualization with the use of dedicated software packages (Avizo, MeshLab, Viewbox, RStudio) according to digital requirements.
- D) Setting-up of a protocol based on different necessities (such as research or exposition) to restore incomplete or fragmented specimens by using geometric morphometric approaches.
- E) Conserving in web repository virtually acquired selected anthropological collections for disseminating 3D data as references for skeletal analysis tools and encouraging data sharing and knowledge transmission.
- F) Offering an alternative way to manage this kind of sensitive asset.

[1] Weber, G. W. (2015) Virtual anthropology. *American journal of physical anthropology*, 156, 22–42.

[2] Simmons-Ehrhardt, T. (2021) Open osteology: Medical imaging databases as skeletal collections. *Forensic Imaging*, 26, 200462.

[3] Sorrentino, R, Belcastro, M.G., Figus, C., Stephens, N.B., Turley, K., Harcourt-Smith, W., Ryan, T.M., Benazzi, S. (2020) Exploring sexual dimorphism of the modern human talus through geometric morphometric methods. *PLoS ONE* 15(2): e0229255. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0229255>

[4] O'Higgins, P. The study of morphological variation in the hominid fossil record: biology, landmarks and geometry. *Journal of Anatomy* (2000) 197(1), 103–120.

[5] Gunz, P., Mitteroecker, P., Bookstein, F.L. (2005) Semilandmarks in three dimensions. *Modern morphometrics in physical anthropology*. Springer, pp. 73–98.

[6] Profico, A., Di Vincenzo, F., Bellucci, L., Strani, F., Tafuri, M. A., Manzi, G. (2016). Advances in virtual archaeology: Research, preservation, and dissemination. In *IMEKO International Conference on Metrology for Archeology and Cultural Heritage, MetroArcheo 2016* (Vol. 2016–October, pp. 89–94). IMEKO–International Measurement Federation Secretariat.

7. Design of a communication plan and a public engagement strategy for CH assets

Background

The *Guidelines on design of a communication plan and a public engagement strategy for CH assets* (hereinafter referred to as the *Guidelines*) aim to facilitate the dissemination of knowledge derived from the multidisciplinary activities carried out by the Spoke 6's research teams. They were prepared with the main purpose of promoting cultural participation as a factor of social cohesion and sustainability and consequentially improving citizens' lives.

The *Guidelines* targets preventive conservation as case study since it is a common ground to the Spoke 6's different research projects.

The *Guidelines* are intended to educate on preventive restoration and build and grow awareness on its importance, its sustainability, and its effectiveness. They are meant to engage two main

different types of audience, on the one hand stakeholders and CH experts, on the other general public therefore communication strategies will be tailored on the target audience.

Guidelines on communication strategy for stakeholders and CH experts

Heritage conservation is gradually changing from being a limited activity focused on emergency intervention or remedial conservation to preventive conservation, that encompasses a wide range of measures and actions aimed at avoiding and minimizing future deterioration or loss. These measures and actions are carried out within the context or on the surroundings of an item and are indirect actions not interfering with the materials and structures. Therefore, the main objectives of a communication strategy for stakeholders and CH experts include:

- Promoting the shift from restoration carried out in emergency or remedial conservation to conservation plans based on predictive analysis and long-term planning.
- Increasing risks understanding and assessment on a priority scale.
- Gaining technical tools for effective project management.
- Gaining methodological tools to get conservation feasible and sustainable.
- Gaining methodological tools for enhancing and sharing experiences.

Since the target audience – stakeholders and CH expert – is already educated, communication can be articulate in a specialising training programme that envisages study days and seminars, such as:

- study days to engage the scientific community, to discuss and share experiences with national and international CH experts. Main focus: preventive conservation in different contexts: diffuse cultural heritage and architectural landscape.
- Open seminars on how to design a conservation project: law regulations’ analysis, disciplinary framework and definition of a scientific vocabulary; identification of different technical competences and professionals.
- Open seminars on how to estimate cost of a conservation project and to drawing up a medium/long-term economic management plan.
- Open seminars on design, management, and maintenance of historical buildings.
- Open seminars on environmental sustainability, new materials for conservation and technological innovation for preventive conservation.
- Open seminars on vulnerability assessment and risk assessment, identification of priorities of intervention with respect to threatening scenarios.
- Open seminars on fundraising plans for CH, how to engage organizations, volunteers, neighbourhood communities.
- Open seminars on crowdfunding: how to encourage donations, law regulations and tax scheme’s analysis, case study. How to communicate crowdfunding: social media, website, newsletters

Those events will allow attendants to:

- Disseminate the importance of preventive conservation and contribute to train new skills and professionals.
- Develop and strengthen networks.
- Create new opportunities for collaboration.

Guidelines on communication strategy for general public

Communicating and enhancing preventive conservation are difficult tasks since very frequently that is a much less visible action than restoration, but it is pivotal that knowledge and awareness

on preventive conservation trickle down from stakeholders and CH experts – broadly speaking the scientific community – to general public. Therefore, the main objectives of a communication strategy include:

- Identifying local communities and interested parties.
- Interacting with local communities and interested parties.
- Promoting school education.
- Promoting public participation to facilitate communication among experts of different disciplines related to the heritage.

Communication for general public can be articulate in online and offline activities, such as:

- Study days to communicate in clear, jargon-free language what conservation means: preventive conservation, remedial conservation, and restoration and how they affect the way we access to and enjoy cultural heritage.
- Open seminars focused on local case studies with guided tour to the sites.
- Visual storytelling events with guided tour to the sites.
- Storytelling and podcast.
- Promoting activities, such as dedicated guided tour, preview, press conferences, on local press and specialized media/websites.
- A continuous interaction between social media channels of the involved stakeholders and consistent updates on websites, SM, and newsletters.

Those actions will allow audience to:

- Get a better understanding of human-environment contexts, historic buildings and multi-layered artefacts with a strong cultural value in their current state of conservation.
- Get engaged on a deeper level thanks to the storytelling and visual storytelling that can provide a more immersive experience.

8. Sharing the data: digitisation and platforms

In the field of CH the digitisation of data is strongly related to many methodological problems. To create a system able to manage CH data it is advisable to introduce viable solutions that embrace interpretative aspects and the reliability concept. Such tool has to be capable of satisfying the special data management requirements of CH experts. The challenge is to establish profitable communication between the domains of CH and Computer Science applying the Requirement Engineering statements.

System flexibility remain an overriding priority throughout the design phase arising from the requirement analysis, in order to ensure the capacity to manage and analyse data relating to any type of CH data. Potential management and data sharing applications have to be identified along with the conceptualization of the domain, taking into account also the possible use of ontologies, as the CIDOC–CRM one.

One of the first requirements of such a tool is the legacy data management, that means to allow analysis of the credibility of CH sources, particularly those dating back several decades.

Subjectivity, uncertainty, rational and intuitive variables, and interpretation variation over time are some of the characteristics of CH data, which is important to preserve and, at the same time, to rightly manage during their digitisation. It is also recommended to considering the FAIR principles, that are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable concepts.

A suitable system has to be developed according to the notions of data availability and uniqueness, through the application of standards, including accessibility and interoperability, as well as to encourage data reuse value and potential, without forgetting the concepts of data integrity and reliability.

Bibliography

P. Allison, Dealing with Legacy Data – An introduction, Internet Archaeology 24, 2008.

<https://doi.org/10.11141/ia.24.8>

E.W. Averett, J.M. Gordon, D.B. Counts (eds.), Mobilizing the Past for a Digital Future: The Potential of Digital Archaeology, The Digital Press at the University of North Dakota, North Dakota 2016.

CIDOC–CRM, <https://www.cidoc-crm.org/>, Last Official Version 7.1.2, June 2022.

L. Gitelman (ed.), “Raw Data” is an Oxymoron. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 2013.

K. Pohl, C. Rupp, Requirements Engineering Fundamentals, Rockynook, Santa Barbara 2005.

M.D. Wilkinson et al., The FAIR guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship, Scientific Data 3:160018, 2016.

Platform creation

The platform must respond to a number of needs:

- the use of different types of case studies (artifacts/monuments/sites/landscapes)
- analysis of the types of risk, also based on the physical location
- analysis and description of the building/monument/site
- documentation of the analyzes of the degradation for the purposes of restoration actions
- planning of conservation, restoration and integration of missing parts

Furthermore, it is necessary to consider the possibility of using an already existing platform, possibly based on open source technologies and possibly modularly expandable.

Net of other prerequisites necessary to be able to adequately define the proposals (e.g. types of data available, technologies/servers/other tools available, timing, skills involved, usability studies, etc.), we can think of a possible solution based on a modeling of cultural heritage data that considers the various aspects that characterize them: the physical data of the building/monument/cultural asset; contextual and historical data; the documentation supporting the conservation analyses; etc.

From this point of view, a partial (as it is focused on historic buildings) but interesting solution could be Historical Building Information Modeling (HBIM), a studied and in-depth methodology, and – in a broader sense – considered promising for the documentation, management and conservation of cultural heritage. HBIM derives from Building Information Modeling (BIM), a process for creating and managing information related to a building project throughout its entire life cycle (What is BIM? | NBS (thenbs.com)). Among the numerous application areas, HBIM has found space in documentation (Cheng et al. 2021), in the analysis and simulation of the risk of degradation (Brumana et al. 2017), in augmented and virtual reality (Barazzetti et al. 2015).

Starting from HBIM, various proposals have been made on the definition of methodologies and tools (such as web services and platforms) to create, manage and maintain the data foreseen by the HBIM model (3D representation, documentation, physical data, contextual data, etc.). For more information see Bruno & Roncella (2019), the NUBES project (De Luca et al. 2012), AIOLI (Bruno & Roncella 2018), BIM3DSG (Fassi et al. 2015), the BIMServer.center platforms (BIMserver.center BIM in the cloud.) and BIMServer (GitHub – opensourceBIM/BIMserver: The open source BIMserver platform), BIMData (BIMData – easily integrated Open BIM tools) and ARK-BIM (Diara & Rinaudo 2021).

Among the factors that complicate the diffusion and use of HBIM, we mention: the rather complex technical requirements required for the 3D modeling of objects with irregular surfaces and lines; the lack of common references and guidelines on data management; and the difficulty in codifying the cultural meaning of tangible and intangible elements as data that can be analyzed and interpreted.

A possible solution to the second and third points is represented by the use of ontologies to support the data model envisaged by HBIM. In the field of cultural heritage, the reference ontology is certainly CIDOC-CRM (International Council of Documentation Conceptual Reference Model) (Versions of the CIDOC-CRM | CIDOC CRM), a fundamental ontology that provides definitions and formal structures for representation of the information used in the documentation of cultural heritage. Some examples of the use of CIDOC-CRM in the HBIM context have been documented in Pauwels et al. (2013), Quattrini et al (2017), Zhang & Issa (2012), Yang et al. (2019), Previtali et al. (2020), and Acierno et al. (2016).

Depending on the availability of monitoring technologies, another solution to consider concerns the integration and use of Digital Twin technologies, i.e. the creation of a digital copy of a real object, connected on one side to knowledge bases which contain the information concerning the object, and on the other hand to the sensors which provide real-time data relating to its physical state. For more information on the integration between the HBIM model and real-time data from sensors, see Jouan & Hallot (2019).

References

Acierno, Marta, Stefano Cursi, Davide Simeone, e Donatella Fiorani. «Architectural Heritage Knowledge Modelling: An Ontology-Based Framework for Conservation Process». *Journal of Cultural Heritage* 24 (1 marzo 2017): 124–33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2016.09.010>.

Barazzetti, L., F. Banfi, R. Brumana, D. Oreni, M. Previtali, e F. Roncoroni. «HBIM and Augmented Information: Towards a Wider User Community of Image and Range-Based Reconstructions». In *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, XL-5-W7:35–42. Copernicus GmbH, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprsarchives-XL-5-W7-35-2015>.

Brumana, R., S. Della Torre, D. Oreni, M. Previtali, L. Cantini, L. Barazzetti, A. Franchi, e F. Banfi. «HBIM CHALLENGE AMONG THE PARADIGM OF COMPLEXITY, TOOLS AND PRESERVATION: THE BASILICA DI COLLEMAGGIO 8 YEARS AFTER THE EARTHQUAKE (L’AQUILA)». In *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, XLII-2-W5:97–104. Copernicus GmbH, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLII-2-W5-97-2017>.

Bruno, N., e R. Roncella. «A RESTORATION ORIENTED HBIM SYSTEM FOR CULTURAL HERITAGE DOCUMENTATION: THE CASE STUDY OF PARMA CATHEDRAL». In *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, XLII-2:171–78. Copernicus GmbH, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLII-2-171-2018>.

Bruno, Nazarena, e Riccardo Roncella. «HBIM for Conservation: A New Proposal for Information Modeling». *Remote Sensing* 11, fasc. 15 (gennaio 2019): 1751. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11151751>.

Cheng, Ying-Mei, Chiao-Ling Kuo, e Chia-Ching Mou. «Ontology-Based HBIM for Historic Buildings with Traditional Woodwork in Taiwan». *Journal of Civil Engineering and Management* 27, fasc. 1 (12 gennaio 2021): 27–44. <https://doi.org/10.3846/jcem.2021.14115>.

De Luca, Livio, Chawee Busayarat, Chiara Stefani, Philippe Véron, e Michel Florenzano. «A Semantic-Based Platform for the Digital Analysis of Architectural Heritage». *Computers & Graphics, Virtual Reality in Brazil*, 35, fasc. 2 (1 aprile 2011): 227–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cag.2010.11.009>.

Diara, Filippo, e Fulvio Rinaudo. «ARK-BIM: Open-Source Cloud-Based HBIM Platform for Archaeology». *Applied Sciences* 11, fasc. 18 (gennaio 2021): 8770. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11188770>.

Jouan, Pierre-André, e Pierre Hallot. «DIGITAL TWIN: A HBIM-BASED METHODOLOGY TO SUPPORT PREVENTIVE CONSERVATION OF HISTORIC ASSETS THROUGH HERITAGE SIGNIFICANCE AWARENESS». *International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences* XLII-2, fasc. 2019 (23 agosto 2019). <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLII-2-W15-609-2019>.

Pauwels, Pieter, Rens Bod, Danilo Di Mascio, e Ronald De Meyer. «Integrating building information modelling and semantic web technologies for the management of built heritage information». In *2013 Digital Heritage International Congress (DigitalHeritage)*, 1:481–88, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1109/DigitalHeritage.2013.6743787>.

Previtali, Mattia, Raffaella Brumana, Chiara Stanga, e Fabrizio Banfi. «An Ontology-Based Representation of Vaulted System for HBIM». *Applied Sciences* 10, fasc. 4 (gennaio 2020): 1377. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10041377>.

Quattrini, Ramona, Roberto Pierdicca, e Christian Morbidoni. «Knowledge-Based Data Enrichment for HBIM: Exploring High-Quality Models Using the Semantic-Web». *Journal of Cultural Heritage* 28 (1 novembre 2017): 129–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2017.05.004>.

Yang, Xiucheng, Pierre Grussenmeyer, Mathieu Koehl, Helene Macher, Arnadi Murtiyoso, e Tania Landes. «Review of Built Heritage Modelling: Integration of HBIM and Other Information Techniques». *Journal of Cultural Heritage* 46 (1 novembre 2020): 350–60.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2020.05.008>.

Yang, Xiucheng, Yi-Chou Lu, Arnadi Murtiyoso, Mathieu Koehl, e Pierre Grussenmeyer. «HBIM Modeling from the Surface Mesh and Its Extended Capability of Knowledge Representation». *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information* 8, fasc. 7 (luglio 2019): 301.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi8070301>.

Zhang, Le, e Raja R. A. Issa. «Ontology-Based Partial Building Information Model Extraction». *Journal of Computing in Civil Engineering* 27, fasc. 6 (1 novembre 2013): 576–84.

[https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CP.1943-5487.0000277](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CP.1943-5487.0000277).

PART II – A few case studies

1. The Pompei project

PE 5, SPOKE 6. University Federico II of Naples

Renata Picone (coordinator), Fabio Mangone, Vincenzo Morra, Valentina Russo

1.1. Analysis and description of the artifact/monument/site.

To decline its project, the Federico II unit in Spoke 6 chose as a case study the Casa of Arianna, located in the Regio VII insula IV of the Archaeological Park of Pompeii. The Domus represents, with its 1700 m², one of the most majestic examples of dwelling inside the Park. The complex has two entrances, occupying the internal depth of the Insula.

Most likely, in 79 AD the House of Arianna, also called House of the Colored Capitals because of the decorations that have been found, included about 70 different units on the ground floor alone and organized around three distribution areas: the atrium, the central peristyle and the North peristyle. The main entrance, located on Via della Fortuna at number 51, had rich tuff capitals with depictions of Satyrs and Maenads, placed to crown the jambs. After the entrance you entered a large Doric peristyle, with by 24 columns made in uncertain work and covered in stucco, on which there are several rooms used as workplaces and partly as *ergastulum* of the oil workshop.

The central peristyle, on the other hand, is punctuated by 16 Ionic columns in tuff, on which the rooms of the large apsidal exedra open and to the west a wing decorated with a travertine flake floor with a vermiculatum emblem, depicting a marine scene. Among the most important rooms in this sector of the house should be counted the oecus, accessible from the communication corridor between the central peristyle and the Tuscan atrium, in which are preserved, on the south wall, paintings in IV Style, and “room 24” in which a decoration was found, also in IV Style, depicting the scene of “Dionysus discovers Ariadne in Naxos”, now kept at the MANN Museum, which suggested one of the conventional titles of the house.

On the opposite side is located the entrance to the Tuscan atrium, which, due to its position on Via degli Augustali and its proximity to the Macellum, is to be identified with the service sector of the domus. Despite the servile function of the rooms, it is worth mentioning the “room 7”, located on the western front, in which there is a painting in IV Style depicting Apollo and Daphne.

1.2. Documentation of the degradation analysis for the purposes of restoration actions

In order to carry out a correct reading of the state of conservation of the House of Arianna it is necessary to face the study of construction techniques and materials present. This is an essential part of the cognitive process of historic buildings, as the values that characterize them are

recognized. These values must be identified with a view to their conservation for use by future generations. The understanding and the ability to recognize the construction techniques, with which the different parts of the domus were made, have allowed us to formulate a first hypothesis on what may have been the causes that led the various architectural elements to degrade. Through a synoptic reading it was possible to divide the different types of masonry, used for the high and columns, the mosaic floors and the few surviving frescoes.

Among the walls have been identified:

- ***Opus quadratum***

Masonry characterized by the use of squared blocks of limestone bound with mortar.

- ***Opus incertum***

Masonry consists of fragments of limestone or lava of irregular shape of medium size.

- ***Opus listatum***,

Masonry composed of rows of bricks held together by mortar.

- ***Opus vittatum***

Masonry in medium-sized squared blocks of limestone bonded with mortar.

- ***Opus mixtum vittatum latericum***

Masonry consists of rows of brick alternating with small blocks of limestone bound by mortar.

Among the pavements have been identified:

- ***Cocciopesto with insertions of tiles***

Flooring in crushed red earthenware with mosaic tiles with geometric patterns.

- ***Beaten in white scales***

Mixed wrought paving of marble chips and river pebbles

- ***Mosaic flooring***

Flooring consisting of a geometric mosaic with black and white bichromes

The preliminary reading of the critical issues of the Domus di Arianna has identified, in particular, three themes on which to set the research:

- a) **the safety of the "free" columns**
- b) **the restoration of frescoes and surface decorations**
- c) **the restoration of mosaic floors**

1.3. Planning of the different types of conservation and restoration interventions

The proposed research aims to rethink the conservation and use of the demonstrator archaeological site in the light of the need posed by the health emergency, combining the instances of conservation with those of a perception of the archaeological heritage in safety. To this end, the project aims to build a web-based "enabling digital platform" for the knowledge, restoration, use, management and safety of the archaeological site, which allows a transition from a segmented approach to a horizontal one, defining a digital ecosystem of cultural heritage that reconnects all the actors involved in the process, enabling the exchange of information, also with the public, through digital information modeling technologies.

In this collaborative network model, value is produced thanks to the relationships between the subjects involved with a centrality of the user that appears as one of the main objectives for the heritage to produce positive social and economic effects. In this vision, innovative technologies allow:

1. new practices of active participation in cultural heritage;
2. a broader understanding of educational content related to cultural heritage;

3. the digitalization of restoration and conservation processes and of the various risks;
4. the equipment of open spaces for post-Covid use;
5. the implementation of *Facility Management* processes.

The final objective is to experiment with an interoperable digital platform related to the archaeological site capable of intercepting the modified needs of restoration, use, enhancement and management of the archaeological site, aligning the cultural heritage sector with the technological evolution that is emerging in the productive and professional world, contributing to transparency and timeliness of processes, and establishing a real dialogue and exchange between the actors, capable of enhancing the potential of enabling technologies for both product and process innovations, with a positive impact on the quality of the project and on the interventions to be carried out on the archaeological heritage. This is in order to reduce uncontrolled spaces of technical and decision-making discretion, while safeguarding, thanks to the transparency, interoperability and wider accessibility of the platform, the irreducible margins of cultural and scientific autonomy involved in every segment of the process, so as to optimize costs and procedures for safeguarding and conservation of cultural heritage.

2. The Baia Project (UniSOB)

PE 05 CHANGES – SPOKE 06

UNIVERSITA' SUOR ORSOLA BENINCASA DI NAPOLI (UNISOB)

Study area: Parco Archeologico delle Terme di Baia

(Comune di Bacoli – provincia di Napoli, via Sella di Baia, 22 – 80070)

<http://www.pafleg.it/it/4388/localita/51/parco-archeologico-delle-terme-di-baia>

The archaeological complex is located in the Campi Flegrei area (Fig. 1) between Pozzuoli and Bacoli; it is an extraordinary testimony of the Roman era, a thermal area (corresponding to the hilly part of the original area, of which a submerged part also still exists), transformed over the centuries by various and periodic bradyseismic phenomena.

The important excavations of the complex were carried out since the 1940s (cf. A. Maiuri, *I Campi Flegrei*, Poligrafico di Stato, Rome 1981), revealing an overlapping of buildings, villas and thermal complexes, that span a historical period complexes from the late Republican era to the Severan imperial period (end of the 2nd – first decades of the 3rd century AD).

For bibliographical references see: *I Campi Flegrei*, edited by G.C. Alisio, Franco di Mauro publisher, Sorrento (NA) 2003; S. Di Liello, *Il paesaggio dei Campi flegrei tra metafora e realtà*, Electa Napoli, Naples 2005.

The most evident effects of bradyseism, with the submarine lowering of the ground, are dated between the III and V century. A.D. (late empire). The ancient bay was largely submerged by the sea towards the VII– VIII AD. Among the most significant buildings, some buildings with domed vaults such as the so-called are worth mentioning. Temples of Diana, Venus and Mercury (wrongly first defined as places of worship, but actually spa facilities).

For the choice of the site, previous activity already carried out under the agreement affects con il Parco Archeologico di Baia:

<http://www.pafleg.it/>

For this identification, see also the educational restoration site (January–November 2022):

https://www.unisob.na.it/ateneo/restauro/attivita0_05.pdf

Among the objectives there is the interpretation and contextualization of the data to arrive at the definition of a common Operational Protocol for the conservation, restoration and scheduled maintenance of the buildings indicated as a research topic among all the units that make up Spoke 6.

On the basis of a common operational experience, it will be possible to exercise a conscious valorisation and use of the area with a tourist-cultural dimension. Another possible initiative is the periodic and public visit of the restoration sites (open air) for greater awareness of the cultural heritage and greater sensitivity and awareness of the issues relating to the protection of cultural heritage.

(Ref. Restorer activities of the Professional Training Paths active at RESTAURO_UNISOB: PFP1 Frescoes_Stonestones; PFP2 Tele_Legno; PFP4 Metals_Ceramics).

Study area UNISOB

A) IDENTIFICATION OF THE CASE STUDY

The Mercury sector, located in the northern area of the site, owes its name to the famous circular building, consisting of a thermal environment, located in the large archaeological area.

This building is a reference and study monument and has been the subject of graphic

reproductions, including prints, gouaches, and engravings by artists and travelers of the "Grand Tour" since the mid-18th century. From the descriptions of the eighteenth century, it is possible to reconstruct the original structure that resulted, with a central plan with six niches (four of which are semi-circular) and an upper cover equipped with a central "lumen" with a dual function (thermodynamics and compartment for lighting internal, Fig. 4). Inside, in front of the entrance, there were two thermal rooms, partially flooded by spring and sea water, with the further presence of basement rooms with the presence of frescoes.

Among the research objectives are:

Proposed investigative reconstructions of the "Mercury sector" (planimetric and virtual using new technologies);

- documentary studies relating to the planimetric configuration of the spa area and its surroundings (historical cartography, iconography of the places, IGM 20th century plans) for the reconstruction of the original buildings and the architectural and urban configuration;
- study of urban stratifications for the fruition and enhancement of the site which, starting from the second half of the twentieth century, has undergone various and substantial transformations related to the building and infrastructure heritage (road network and construction of the Circumflegrea railway line) adjacent to the archaeological area and museum.

Hypotheses of graphic reconstructions are expected for the urban transformations of the site and its surroundings involving various disciplinary sectors and aim at enhancing transversal scientific contributions. Therefore, the study and analysis of documentary sources, historical cartography, as well as the periegetic, iconographic, and literary sources, and contemporary architectural documents are essential.

The characterization will concern the architectural-archaeological, diagnostic, restorative, conservative and maintenance aspects; in this sense, the presence of expert professionals in: history of architecture (ICAR/18), biology (BIO/01), expert in archaeometry, professional restorers of works of art, professionals in construction techniques of materials (ICAR /19) and in systems for detecting the contemporary state (ICAR/17). Historical-documentary investigations are foreseen for the knowledge of the territory and, in particular for the aspects relating to the archaeological pre-existence connected to the existing architectural stratification.

Preliminary diagnostic investigations are planned for the characterization of the building through architectural survey and mapping of the present degradation with the verification of the state of conservation of the building through the detection of the state of the places with expert systems (HBIM).

B) RISK ANALYSIS

It is an archaeological site, open to the public, susceptible to a risk factor of biological contamination due to the tourist flow. Furthermore, the marked urbanization of the surroundings of the archaeological and museum area, which took place starting from the modern age, and irreversibly (from a building point of view) in the second half of the twentieth century, determines a situation of urban stratification of rare environmental alteration.

C) ANALYSIS AND DESCRIPTION OF THE BUILDING FOR RESTORATION

Knowledge of the botanical heritage and of the scientific (BIO/01) and bibliographic findings relating to the historiographical literature of the dynamics of urban development and historical-architectural stratification (ICAR/18) of the Campi Flegrei area in the context of the Campania Region (ref. Digital ecosystem of the Campania Region:

<https://cultura.regione.campania.it/it/web/guest/home>). Analysis of ancient construction techniques (ICAR/19) of the environments selected for research is foreseen.

The different characterization of the artifacts, distinguished by clay, metal, stone and coloring matter, could constitute a sampling of data useful for defining different aspects of the research. Scientific investigations in order to evaluate the typology of the constituent materials (organic and inorganic) of the archaeological, architectural and artistic artifacts identified as an object of research.

Analysis of the substrate with scanning electron microscopy (SEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray fluorescence (XRF), optical microscopy on stratigraphic glossy section (OM); molecular biology analysis in order to characterize all biological communities and place them in the environmental context, analysis of soluble salts and chemical investigations of organic and non-organic components through the use of instruments such as gas chromatography with mass (GC-MS) and Fourier transform spectroscopy (FT-IR)¹⁹. Thermographic and colorimetric surveys in collaboration with the CNR-ISASI (Institute of Applied Sciences and Intelligent Systems "E. Caianiello") of Pozzuoli: <https://www.cnr.it/it/istituto/O24/istituto-di-scienze-applicate-e-sistemi-intelligenti-eduardo-caianiello-isasi>, a multi-year collaboration already activated with the RESTAURO_UNISOB degree course: <https://www.unisob.na.it/ateneo/restauro/index.htm?vr=1>

D) CONSERVATION AND RESTORATION INTERVENTION PLANNING

On the basis of the results obtained from the diagnostic investigations (referred to in letters C-D) the planning of a type of intervention (maintenance, conservation and/or restoration) will be evaluated also thanks to the planning of innovative protocols for the elimination of bio-encrustations through innovative and non-innovative methodologies invasive (use of UV-C and microwaves). These interventions will be conducted by expert figures of restorers and diagnosticians (BIO/01, L-ANT/10) with decennial experience in archaeometry.

3. The Royal Museums in Turin (UniTO)

¹⁹ Available instrumentation already present in the laboratory **DIAGNOSTICA_UNISOB (scienze e tecniche applicate ai beni culturali)**: Diffrazione ai raggi X (Miniflex Rigaku) / Microscopia elettronica a scansione (Vega3, Tescan) / Fluorescenza ai raggi X (Assing Lithos) / Spettroscopia FT-IR (Thermofischer Nicolet IS 10) / Gas cromatografia con massa (Thermofischer ISQ Tracer 1300) / Microscopia ottica su sezione lucida (Nikon Eclipse L 150).

4. Monuments and fountains in the city of Turin public space (1563)

Monuments and fountains in the city of Turin public space.

Outdoor cultural heritage assets: scheduled maintenance plans and operational management protocols

Project overview

The project *Monuments and fountains in the city of Turin public space* aims to define a scheduled conservation plan and a coordinated and continuous maintenance plan for cultural heritage assets located in public spaces, therefore subjects to environmental factors (climate changes) and anthropic factors (social changes). Also, it pursues the goal of designing an operational management protocol that meets the cultural heritage assets’ conservations requirements as well as provides the public administration with new sustainable and effective management and organisational solutions.

The aim is to promote technological and disciplinary development in the conservation field, supporting the transition from restoration carried out in emergency to conservation plans based on predictive analysis and long-term planning. This way, a virtuous cycle of inspection-monitoring-intervention would be triggered, and an easier and agile management of cultural heritage assets would be established.

To develop the above project Fondazione 1563 draws on its expertise in cultural project management, gained through its long-lasting experience in fostering research in the humanities and its specialisation in conceiving, developing and realising conservation and enhancement projects of archival, book and historical-artistic heritage assets. Fondazione 1563 can also benefit from the collaboration of entities of its network, such as the Fondazione Centro Conservazione e Restauro dei Beni Culturali “La Venaria Reale”, which carries out training, research, conservation and restoration activities, and the Fondazione LINKS, which is dedicated to high-tech projects’ R&D. Thanks to this network, the Fondazione 1563 is positive that with the *Monuments and fountains in the city of Turin public space* project it will be able to deal with the Spoke 6’s work packages and deliver many of the required deliverables with a vertical approach.

	Work packages: SPOKE 6 – HISTORY, CONSERVATION AND RESTORATION OF CULTURAL HERITAGE	Guidelines on design of a scheduled maintenance plan and an operational management protocol for cultural heritage assets in public spaces, according to the <i>Monuments and fountains in the city of Turin public space</i> project
1	WP1: Anamnesi	Defining the current situation of cultural heritage assets being studied Mapping the context: collecting systematized information to identify the current situation of the studied cultural heritage assets in terms of

		conservation status.
	WP2: Knowledge	<p>Technical-scientific planning: in-depth technical-scientific studies useful to defining a <i>Management protocol of degradation and preventive maintenance manual</i>; identification of HW and SW technological solutions that meet effectiveness and efficiency requirements, functional to carry out the <i>Protocol</i>.</p> <p>Needs analysis: identifying criticality on a management level and technological gaps, that could hinder the development and fulfilment of conservation and preventive maintenance plans for the mapped cultural heritage assets and their long-term management.</p> <p>Vulnerability assessment: identifying case studies; collecting documentation; formulating diagnostic plans based on the gathered documentation and preliminary observations results.</p>
	WP3: Restoration	Testing the <i>Management protocol</i> and operational tools through a pilot project.
	WP4: Monitoring	Carrying out the pilot project.
	WP5: Sharing	Identifying a platform for digital storage and access to data derived from the preservation plans' development

Deliverables SPOKE 6 – HISTORY, CONSERVATION AND RESTORATION OF CULTURAL HERITAGE	Deliverables according to the <i>Monuments and fountains in the city of Turin public space</i> project
--	---

<p>1</p>	<p>Guidelines for the application of integrated methodologies for the material, technical–constructive, chronological and functional documentation and description of human–environment contexts, historic buildings and multi–layered artefacts with a strong cultural value in their current state of conservation</p>	<p>Defining a descriptive model of the cultural heritage assets’ current situation; defining descriptive entries following the cataloguing standards of the Italian Ministry of Culture and Istituto Centrale per il Catalogo e la Documentazione [Central Institute for Catalogue and Documentation (ICCD)].</p> <p>Defining a model of documentary mapping of the context where the studied cultural heritage assets are located in; description of environmental and anthropic factors.</p>
<p>2</p>	<p>Guidelines for the analysis of the historical study of restoration and conservation interventions in relation to the vulnerability of the structures, the durability of the materials, the phenomena of abiotic and biotic degradation of artifacts in the geo–environmental and climatic evolution of the context</p>	<p>Defining a model of documentary mapping of previous interventions on the studied cultural heritage assets; surveys, maintenance reports, previous conservation interventions.</p>
<p>3</p>	<p>Technical–scientific report of the database for measurement, archiving, management and analysis of data in support of restoration and conservation strategies</p>	<p>Defining a model of technical mapping: reconnaissance of hardware and software technological solutions for data collection and processing.</p> <p>Developing a digital storage and data management architecture.</p>

<p>4</p>	<p>Guidelines for the application of procedures (including non-destructive), technologies (including non-invasive) and Technical-scientific report on innovative sensing devices and Technical-scientific report on innovative and green materials and environment-sustainable methodologies/procedures for the effective and durable conservation, protection and restoration of cultural heritage</p>	<p>Defining the <i>Management protocol of degradation and preventive maintenance manual.</i></p>
<p>5</p>	<p>Technical-scientific report on automatic or semi-automatic data measurements and analysis algorithms to support the conservation, restoration, and monitoring processes</p>	<p>Reporting on diagnostic studies and predictive models defined and adopted through the pilot project.</p>
<p>6</p>	<p>Technical-scientific report on the creation of semantic digital models according to HBIM and EBIM paradigms to support the analysis, intervention and monitoring processes</p>	<p>Exploring possible applications of H-BIM e Digital Twin technologies.</p>

<p>7</p>	<p>Technical–scientific report of the infrastructure for the remote acquisition of useful data to support the monitoring, analysis and mitigation processes of risk scenarios in relation with territorial, geo–environmental and microclimate changes</p>	<p>Defining the <i>Management protocol of degradation and preventive maintenance manual</i>.</p> <p>Needs analysis with respect to HW and SW solutions.</p>
<p>8</p>	<p>Guidelines for the application of procedural rules for public engagement in the conservation, restoration and monitoring processes of contexts, historic buildings, cultural landscapes and multi–layered artefacts with a strong cultural value</p>	<p>Enhancing elements of environmental sustainability (energy efficiency and conservation), social sustainability (reuse, urban regeneration, active citizen participation) and financial sustainability of scheduled maintenance plans.</p>
<p>9</p>	<p>Technical–scientific report of the knowledge sharing and technology transfer platform</p>	<p>Developing a digital storage and data management architecture.</p>
<p>10</p>	<p>Technical–scientific report of the results achieved in concrete application scenarios</p>	<p><i>Management protocol of degradation and preventive maintenance manual</i>.</p>

5. University of Turin. Pompeii, the House of the Ancient Hunt (VII,4,47) and selection of mobile artefacts (frescoes, mosaics, statues, stuccoes, plaster casts, metals, etc.).

The case study, the various components of which are already included in research activities and operational monitoring and conservation practices, has a high potential to combine archaeological study with advanced technologies for diagnostics, as well as scientific approaches and tools aimed at restoration and preventive conservation, as already verified in completed or ongoing projects. The experience gathered so far, the first results of which were presented in an exhibition held in Venaria Reale and in a volume (*Pompeiana Fragmenta. Conoscere e conservare (a) Pompei. Indagini archeologiche, analisi diagnostiche e restauri*, Torino 2018, ed. by D. Elia e V. Meirano), involved the building context of the Domus della Caccia Antica (VII,4,47) and its decorative apparatus (frescoes, stuccoes, mosaic floors, etc.), as well as a large selection of artefacts from the Park's deposits (statues, stuccoes, plaster casts, metals, frescoes, mosaics, etc.). The activities involved interdisciplinary research groups with the participation of researchers from five UniTo departments (Chemistry, Physics, Earth Sciences, Life Sciences and Systems Biology, Historical Studies), together with restorers.

The theme of restoration and conservation in the archaeological field thus represents a line of research that has seen an in-depth theoretical and methodological reflection mature within the Turin team, aimed at intervention practices, as well as multiple methods of diagnostic analysis, conducted both on surfaces in situ and on artefacts preserved in the laboratory.

These experiences will be useful in particular for

- define tools and good practices for conservation status assessment and risk analysis;
- develop methodologies for the evaluation and monitoring of restoration interventions;
- develop methodological reflections on restoration, its dissemination and preventive conservation.

In the light of the process already dealt with, the intention is to develop

- analyses aimed at determining materials and techniques
- determination of agents connected with degradation processes
- monitoring of degradation processes
- monitoring of previous restoration work
- definition of intervention protocols
- comparison of intervention approaches and techniques applied on a multi-layered site:

archaeological stratification/layering of natural and anthropic interventions on surfaces from the moment of discovery to the present day (1833–2023)

- comparison and reflection with respect to the various experiences gained at the Pompeii site in the field of restoration and conservation, in particular within the recent Great Pompeii Project
- inclusion in the capillary conservation documentation projects launched by the Park, through the creation of special conservation survey sheets, in order to enhance the development of planned conservation plans that have already been activated.

Contatti di riferimento

Pietro Militello

Professore ordinario

Telefono: +39 347 373 5308

Mail: pietro.militello@unict.it